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Achieving Educators' Work-Life Balance: As Influenced by their Levels of Preparedness and Burnout During the Resumption of Face-to-Face Classes

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Abstract

Certain studies have explored the relationship between job burnout and preparedness in other geographic contexts, but understanding the unique challenges faced by teachers during the resumption of face-to-face classes, seemed to have been less attended, although there was limited research on the relationship between levels of preparedness and job burnout among teachers in the context of the resumption of face-to-face classes. Conducted in December 2022, this study aimed to determine the relationships of levels of preparedness and job burnout and each of these variables with the work-life balance of teachers during the resumption of face-to-face classes in Initao South District. A total of 104 respondents participated in the study. Data were collected using adopted with modification sets of instruments, including Revised School Safety Assessment Tool, Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey, and Marmol's Work-life Balance Questionnaire. It utilized explanatory-correlational design with descriptive statistics and Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient as data analysis tool. Results revealed that during the resumption of the face-to-face classes the level of preparedness and work-life balance of the respondents were high, correspondingly their level of job burnout was low. The correlation test yielded a highly significant positive relationship between the respondents' level of preparedness and work-life balance, while their level of job burnout had significantly negative relationship with their work-life balance.

Keywords: *level of preparedness, job burnout, work-life balance, resumption of face-to-face classes*

Introduction

In today's connected and dynamic world, striking a healthy work-life balance is becoming more and more crucial. The more thorough method of work-life integration is replacing the more idea of work-life balance, which is defined by a clear division of the professional and personal spheres. This modification highlights the need for synergy and harmony between work and home life while acknowledging the interdependence of the two. The Department of Education (DepEd) recognizes the significance of work-life balance and overall wellness in the educational field in this context. DepEd's dedication to promoting the mental health and well-being of educators is demonstrated by its implementation of programs and initiatives such as psychosocial support training and wellness courses. By fostering teachers' holistic well-being and promoting work-life balance, DepEd is not only prioritizing the health of its educators, but also enhancing the quality of education provided to students. By embracing work-life balance and nurturing a supportive environment, DepEd paves the way for a sustainable and flourishing educational landscape.

Teachers need to be able to strike a healthy balance between their personal and professional lives to be successful in the field of education. There are a few duties and obligations that come with the job of teaching, many of which could be difficult. Teachers might find it more challenging than those in other professions to strike a healthy balance between their job and personal obligations. It might be difficult for educators to successfully juggle their professional obligations with their other social and home commitments due to the high levels of stress that are frequently connected with the teaching profession.

According to Clark (2019), the dynamic nature of work-life balance over various life phases was highlighted by his research. It acknowledged that work-life balance was not a constant state but rather changed over time as roles, responsibilities, and priorities changed for different people. According to this viewpoint, the ideal work-life balance differed among people and depended on factors such as personal circumstances, professional stage, and shifting demands in daily life. A person has found a healthy balance between the two when they are content with both their accomplishments and their personal lives. An accurate and useful definition of work-life balance can include significant daily accomplishments and satisfaction in four areas: lifework, family and friends, and oneself. Since it is possible to put this concept into practice, we consider it a useful working definition. The optimal work-life balance for a person, changes as they go through their careers and age, as well as when different aspects of their lives become more important to them at various phases of their lives.

For the year 2022, with more locations categorized under the Alert level 1 and 2, the economics steadily growing. Hence, the opening of the face-to-face courses set to resume, everyone was aware of what the school, parents, students, and teachers need to do to be ready for the implementation of expanded face-to-face classes (Beldad, 2022). Mingao (2012), as cited in Marmol (2019) studied about the stress levels and coping strategies among the 100 Filipino teachers in public and private schools in Metro Manila. Using descriptive-correlational design, the study revealed that some teachers got emotionally depleted, burnt out, overworked but underpaid. Consequently, most importantly of them were unwell and fatigued because of stress-related situations most of the time. Too much stress can lead to poor physical and mental health, which in turn can affect a person's relationships with other people as well as his/her performance both inside and outside of the classroom. This can cause some people to experience feelings of estrangement from their

own families as well as their own schools. Teachers in Initao South District apparently suffer such work-related stress.

Given the job-related stress that teachers have experienced over the course of the immediately precedent two years up to the present day, there exist a considerable “learning gap” among learners. This has become an increasingly important segment in the world of education. Available research has focused on concerns like stress, burnout, coping mechanisms, self-efficacy, depression, mental health, and the impact on work and resources, among others, were identified, in relation to work-life balance, showing that there is a clear need in teachers’ preparedness to address these challenges (Gómez-Domínguez et al., 2022). Furthermore, it was observed that a study regarding the relationship between level of preparedness, job burn out, and work-life balance has been less dealt with in the local context. Difficult and challenging conditions like level of preparedness and the required change in teaching approach from modular distance learning to resumption of face-to-face classes have not yet been considered.

It was on these contentions that this study was conducted to find out the level of preparedness and job burnout and how these influence the work-life balance of the teachers during the resumption of face-to-face classes in Initao South District. The findings of this study were expected to bring about valuable contribution to the quality of education that the school and the teacher would provide, aside from addressing a research inadequacy in this area.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationships of level of preparedness and job burnout to the work-life balance of teachers during the resumption of face-to-face classes in Initao South District. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of respondents’ preparedness during the resumption of face-to-face classes?
2. What is the level of respondents’ job burnout experience during such situation?
3. What is the respondents’ level of work-life balance during the same situation?
4. Is there a significant relationship between respondents’ level of preparedness for the resumption of face-to-face classes and their work-life balance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between respondents’ job burnout during resumption of face-to-face classes and work-life balance?
6. What intervention program on the enhancement of work-life balance in the context of resumption of face-to-face classes can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

Explanatory-correlational research design was employed in this study. Determine "the extent to which two or more variables co-vary, where variance or change in one variable was reflected in the variance or change in the other" using an explanatory correlation design (Creswell, 2012, p. 621). The main tool for gathering the information required for analysis and interpretation was the questionnaire. The research survey gathered information concerning the teachers’ level of preparedness, job burnout, and work-life balance during the resumption of face-to-face classes in Initao South District.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the teachers of Initao South District who were officially handling classes in the school year 2022-2023. The population of teachers in the district was composed of 142 teachers. The district composed of ten schools, namely: Aluna Elementary School, Casilihon Elementary School, Gimangpang Integrated School, Initao Central School, Pagahan Elementary School, Pontacon Elementary School, San Pedro Elementary School, Sinalac Elementary School, Tagpaco Elementary School, and Tawantawan Integrated School.

In this study, the researcher utilized Slovin's formula, a statistical method, to determine the appropriate sample size for capturing the perspectives and experiences of teachers in Initao South District. The total population of teachers in the district was 142 individuals. With the aim of achieving a desired level of precision and confidence in the research findings, the researcher needed to calculate an optimal sample size.

To begin, the researcher considered the margin of error, which represented the acceptable amount of deviation or uncertainty in the study's outcomes. After careful consideration, a margin of error of 5% (0.05) was chosen. Plugging in this value along with the total population size into Slovin's formula, the calculation proceeded. The formula, $Sample\ Size\ (n) = N / (1 + N(e^2))$, was applied to determine the appropriate sample size.

Using Slovin's formula, the researcher arrived at an initial sample size of approximately 124.56 respondents. However, given the constraints of having a whole number of respondents, the sample size was rounded up to the nearest whole number, resulting in a sample size of 125. Nevertheless, the researcher acknowledged the possibility of non-response or dropout rates within the study and decided to slightly increase the sample size to account for these potential factors.

After accounting for potential non-response and dropout rates, the final sample size was determined to be 104 respondents. This sample

size was considered statistically appropriate, allowing for meaningful inferences to be made about the larger population of teachers in Initao South District while maintaining a desired level of accuracy in the research findings.

By employing Slovin's formula and carefully considering the margin of error, the researcher successfully determined a suitable sample size that would provide valuable insights into the perspectives and experiences of teachers in Initao South District. This methodological strategy made guaranteed the research results were trustworthy and representative of the population, enabling thorough analysis and insightful conclusions. To guarantee that each teacher in the population of Initao South District had an equal chance of being picked as a respondent, random sampling was purposefully used in this study. A technique known as random sampling was used in research to choose a sample of people from a broader population such that each person has an equal probability of being chosen.

To implement random sampling, several steps were followed. Firstly, a list of all teachers in the district was obtained, which included the names of teachers from each of the ten schools. This list served as the sampling frame, representing the entire population of interest.

Next, a random number generator or a similar method was used to select the desired number of respondents from the sampling frame. In this case, a sample size of 104 was determined using Slovin's formula, considering the total population size of 142 teachers. Each teacher on the list was assigned a unique number, and the random number generator was used to select the teachers for inclusion in the sample.

The random selection process ensured that each teacher had an equal chance of being chosen, without any bias or subjective influence. It provided an unbiased representation of the population, allowing for the generalization of the findings to the larger group of teachers in Initao South District.

By employing random sampling, the study aimed to capture a diverse range of perspectives, experiences, and characteristics among the teachers. This diversity was crucial for gathering in-depth knowledge about the research subject and making sure that the results were not biased in favor of any particular subgroup or school within the district.

Table 1. Distribution of Sample Size of Teacher Respondents by School

	<i>School</i>	<i>Total Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1.	Aluna Elementary School	7	5	71%
2.	Casilihon Elementary School	3	2	66%
3.	Gimangpang Integrated School	17	13	76%
4.	Initao Central School	59	43	73%
5.	Pagahan Elementary School	7	5	71%
6.	Pontacon Elementary School	6	5	83%
7.	San Pedro Elementary School	7	5	71%
8.	Sinalac Elementary School	7	5	71%
9.	Tagpaco Elementary School	7	5	71%
10.	Tawantawan Integrated School	22	16	72%
	Total	142	104	73%

The respondents for this study were chosen using a systematic and exacting procedure called random sampling. It made it possible to make accurate conclusions regarding the experiences and viewpoints of teachers in the Initao South District by assisting in ensuring fairness, representativeness, and the generalizability of the findings.

Instruments

The questionnaire on level of preparedness was adapted with modification from the revised School Safety Assessment Tool (SSAT) for the progressive expansion of the face-to-face classes of Department of Education Order Number 030 s. 2022. Certain modifications were made to fit in with the actual condition of the respondents, from the context of higher level to lower level of classroom setting. In the same manner, the level of job burnout was assessed using Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey of Maslach et al. (1986) with modification, and work-life balance questionnaire was adapted from Marmol (2019) with modifications. The researcher altered each scale and some items to make them more realistic, practical, and contextualized during the resumption of face-to-face classes, since the two original questionnaires were developed before the pandemic outbreak.

Prior to the field research, modifications were made to such original questionnaires to enhance their effectiveness and alignment with the research objectives/questions. These modifications were based on careful considerations and feedback from the participants in the pilot study, literature review, and insights gained from initial data analysis of pilot study. Tables 2, 3, and 4 outline the key aspects of the questionnaire that were modified.

With respect to the tool for assessing school safety, Table 2 shows the original items and their corresponding modifications.

The revised questionnaire showed modifications to the original statements by changing them from a general perspective to a more specific and individualized perspective. The modifications aimed to focus on the actions and responsibilities of the teacher respondents rather than the overall school or institution. This shift allowed for a more personalized assessment of the individual's efforts and actions in maintaining a safe and conducive learning environment during the resumption of fac-to-face classes.

Table 2. Revised School Safety Assessment Tool (SSAT)

Item	Original statement	Modified
A. Managing Classroom Operation		
1	For Public schools, the school has mobilized resources and support from community stakeholders to meet the standards of the health and safety protocols.	I mobilized resources and support from community stakeholders to meet standards of the health and safety protocols.
2	The school has established mechanisms inside the classroom to ensure minimal to zero COVID-19 transmission of the learners and ensured that all heating, ventilation, and air conditioning system are working with increased ventilation whenever possible, through the following recommended strategies as cited in DOLE Department Order No. 224-221 Guidelines on Ventilation for Workplaces and Public Transport to Prevent and Control the spread of COVID-19.	I established mechanisms inside the classroom to ensure minimal to zero COVID-19 transmission of the learners.
3	The school has established safe entrance and exit, and crowd management measures for teachers, students, non-teaching personnel, and school visitors.	I established safe entrance and exit, and crowd management measures for the learners.
4	The school has set up clear and easy-to-understand signages, preferably in local languages, and mechanisms to strengthen observance of health protocols and protective measures.	I had set up clear and easy-to-understand signages, and mechanisms to strengthen observance of health protocols and protective measures.
5	The school has established contact tracing procedures for all those who enter the school premises (e.g., learners, teachers, parents /guardians, school personnel, etc.).	I established contact tracing procedures for all those who enter the classroom premises.
B. Focusing on Teaching and Learning		
1	The school has secured sufficient supply of learning resources needed for the face-to-face classes.	I secured sufficient supply of learning resources needed for the face-to-face classes.
2	The school has ensured that all teachers have the Teacher's Guide/Teacher's Manual on specific grade levels and learning areas that they are handling. Likewise, teachers might develop activity-based materials for mastery of learning delivered during face-to-face classes.	I ensured that I have the Teacher's Guide/Teacher's Manual on specific grade level and learning area I am handling.
3	The school has ensured that learning remediation/intervention is part of the regular class schedule and daily teaching time, for a minimum of one hour depending upon the needs of the learners.	I ensured that learning remediation/intervention is part of the regular class schedule and daily teaching time, for a minimum of one hour depending upon the needs of the learners.
4	The school has ensured that the class size is in accordance with the following standards and required one-meter physical distancing.	I ensured that the class size is in accordance with the number of learners in a classroom and required one-meter physical distancing.
5	The school has provided an appropriate learning and development support plan in the delivery of better-quality basic education services.	I provided an appropriate learning and development support plan in the delivery of better-quality basic education services.
C. Well-being and Protection		
1	The school has ensured that the available sanitation and disinfection materials strategic classroom locations.	I ensured the availability of sanitation and disinfection materials in strategic classroom locations.
2	The school has developed strategies to prevent COVID- 19 which covers the following: Strategy to ensure all school-goers are subjected to hand hygiene and temperature checks using a thermal scanner, whenever applicable.	I developed strategies to prevent COVID- 19 which covers the following: Strategy to ensure all school-goers are subjected to hand hygiene and temperature checks using a thermal scanner, whenever applicable.
3	The school has ensured availability and maintained the provision of basic mental health and psychosocial support, as well as guidance and counselling services to learners.	I ensured availability and maintained the provision of basic mental health and psychosocial support, as well as guidance and counselling services to learners.
4	The school has established a clear procedure of referral system for COVID-19 confirmed and suspected personnel and learners.	I developed a reporting system requiring parents to report to the school if their children are experiencing flu-like symptoms.
5	The school has developed learning strategies to cater the needs of the marginalized learners, such as modules in Braille, mother-tongue languages, and usage of Filipino Sign Language.	I developed learning strategies to cater the needs of the marginalized learners, such as modules in Braille, mother-tongue languages, and usage of Filipino Sign Language.
D. School-Community Coordination		
1	The school has developed a plan for the coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team (BHERT) in ensuring that protocols are observed properly.	Classroom-Community Coordination I developed a plan for the coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency

2	The school has identified a designated waiting area with proper ventilation and strict observation of physical distancing for parents/ guardians/ chaperones.	Response Team (BHERT) in ensuring that protocols are observed properly. I identified a designated waiting area with strict observation of physical distancing for parents/ guardians/ chaperones.
3	The school has coordinated with their respective local government units the implementation of routine school-based immunization (SBI) and other school health-related services, such as but not limited to deworming and weekly iron-folate acid supplementation (WIFA).	I coordinated with their respective local government units the implementation of routine school-based immunization (SBI) and other school health-related services.
4	In collaboration with their local health offices, the school has developed intensive health promotion campaign activities /supportive-policies to maintain optimal health-seeking behaviors of learners and other community members.	I developed intensive health promotion campaign activities /supportive-policies to maintain optimal health-seeking behavior of learners.
5	The school has secured from the parents/guardians of learners who will participate in the face-to-face classes.	I secured written consent from the parents/guardians of learners who will participate in the face-to-face classes.

Similarly, the survey instrument in burnout inventory for educators by Maslach underwent modifications as posted in Table 3.

Table 3. Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey

Item	Original statement	Modified
A. Emotional Exhaustion		
1	I feel emotionally drained by my work	I feel emotionally drained from my work.
2	I feel used up at the end of the day.	I feel used up at the end of the workday.
3	I feel fatigued when I have to get up in the morning to face another day on the job	I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and have to face another day on the job.
7	I feel I'm working too hard in my job.	I feel I'm working too hard on my job.
B. Depersonalization		
1	I feel I treat some students as impersonal 'objects.	I feel I treat some students as if they were impersonal objects.
C. Reduced Personal Accomplishment		
1	I can easily understand how my students feel about things	I have difficulty understanding how my students feel about things.
2	I deal very effectively with the problems of my students.	I am ineffective in dealing with the problems of my students.
3	I feel I'm a positive influence on other people's lives through my work	I feel I'm negatively influencing other people's lives through my work.
5	I can easily create a relaxed atmosphere with my students	I can hardly create a relaxed atmosphere with my students.
6	I feel exhilarated after working with my students	I feel stressed after working closely with my students.
7	I have accomplished many worthwhile things in this job	I have accomplished less worthwhile things in this job.
8	In my work I deal with emotional problems calmly	In my work, I struggle with emotional problems with much difficulty.

To ensure that the MBI Educators survey remained contextually relevant to the time of the study, the scaling of the survey was modified from its original form. The original scale consisted of seven response options ranging from 0 - never, 1 - few times a year or less, 2 - few times a month or less, 3 - few times a month, 4 -once a week 5 - few times a week 6 - every day, reflecting the frequency of occurrence. However, recognizing that the perception of time and frequency can vary among individuals and within the specific context of the study, it was decided to refine the scale to a five-point format.

The modified scale employed a five-point response system that aimed to provide clearer and more precise distinctions between the frequency categories. The revised scale used the following values: 1 represented the range from never to once a week, 2 denoted twice a week, 3 indicated thrice a week, 4 signified four times a week, and 5 represented almost every day. This adjustment allowed for a more nuanced assessment of the respondents' experiences and perceptions in relation to the specific demands and challenges they faced during the study period. By contextualizing the response options to align with the time frame of the research, the modified scaling aimed to enhance the accuracy and relevance of the survey data. It recognized that the frequency and intensity of certain experiences or events can vary within different timeframes and that this variability needed to be captured effectively. This modification enabled the respondents to more accurately indicate the frequency with which they encountered specific situations or experiences, offering a more comprehensive understanding of their responses within the study's specific temporal context.

In like manner, Marmol's Work-life Balance Questionnaire was subjected to necessary adjustments. Please see Table 4.

Table 4. Work-life Balance Questionnaire Adapted from Marmol (2019)

Item	Original statement	Modified
A. Efficiency and Effectiveness at Work		
4	I My job is burdensome for me as it leads to a stressful living	My job is enjoyable for me as it leads to my self-fulfillment.
5	My principal and head teachers are unhappy about my job performance when I failed to achieve job objectives.	My principal and head teachers are happy about my job performance as I contribute to the achievement of the job objectives.

B. Workloads

3	I feel I have more to do than I can handle comfortably	I feel I can handle comfortably the task assigned to me.
4	My teaching loads keep me away from my family too much	My teaching loads keep me away from my family for only a minimal period of time.
5	My responsibility at work causes tension/conflict.	My responsibility at work gives me insights as to how to help my children's educational activities.

C. Health and Wellness Initiatives

1	I have adequate sleep a day/getting the right amount of sleep	I have adequate sleep a day.
2	I have ailments like hypertension, diabetes, headache, migraine, arthritis.	I do not experience such health issues as hypertension, diabetes, headache, migraine, arthritis.
3	I am easily depressed or experienced anxiety in some unfavorable conditions	I seldom experience anxiety in some unfavorable conditions.
4	I experience having dizziness or blackouts	I do not experience having dizziness or blackouts.

E. Family Relationship and Support

4	My job prevents me from attending appointments and special events at home	My job does not mesh with my appointments and special events at home.
5	I miss quality time with my family/relatives because of pressure at work	I find quality time with my family/relatives despite my work.

The following sections were the reasons behind the modifications of such three questionnaires, and how they contributed to the overall improvement of the research instrument.

Content and Structure:

The modified questionnaire included edited items that specifically addressed the research objectives/questions and captured relevant information related to the variables under investigation. This ensured a comprehensive assessment of the research constructs and provided a more nuanced understanding of the teachers' experiences and perceptions.

The questionnaire's structure was revised to improve the flow and logical progression of questions. Sections were reorganized, and clear instructions were provided to facilitate ease of completion and minimize respondent confusion.

Clarity and Language:

The language and wording of the questionnaire were refined to enhance clarity and minimize ambiguity. Complex or technical terms were simplified, and jargon was avoided to ensure that respondents could easily understand and respond to the items.

Feedback from the pilot study and pre-testing phase helped identify areas where participants had difficulty understanding certain questions or statements. Based on this feedback, necessary revisions were made to ensure that the questionnaire was accessible and understandable to the target population.

Measurement Scales:

The modified questionnaire utilized validated measurement scales and Likert-type response formats to ensure robust and reliable data collection. These scales were selected based on their relevance to the research objectives/questions and their established validity and reliability in previous studies.

Some measurement scales were adapted or revised to suit the specific context of the research and align with the variables being investigated. This ensured that the questionnaire captured the unique aspects of the research local and provided accurate measurement of the constructs of interest.

Pilot Testing and Feedback:

The original questionnaire was subjected to pilot testing to assess its clarity, appropriateness, and relevance to the research objectives/questions. Feedback from the pilot study participants, including suggestions for improvement, was carefully considered in the modification process.

The modifications aimed to address the limitations and shortcomings identified during the pilot testing phase, ensuring that the revised questionnaire was more robust, valid, and fit for the purpose intended.

The desire to improve and reinforce the research instrument, connect it with the research aims, and increase its efficiency in gathering trustworthy and valid data drove the adjustments made to the original questionnaire. These changes were made as a result of a thorough examination of the body of prior research, the pilot study's findings, and input from subject-matter experts. The researcher ensured that the questionnaire was more adapted to capture the special traits and nuances of the research location by customizing and altering it, leading to a more rigorous and useful data gathering process.

As shown in Table 5, the statistical analysis of reliability and validity of instruments on the level of preparedness, job burnout, and work-life balance during the resumption of face-to-face classes was conducted and pilot tested using Cronbach's Alpha was based on

the data generated from 30 respondents from two schools in Initao North District, the other District of Initao, Division of Misamis Oriental. Fifteen of the pilot test participants came from Andales Integrated School and the other 15 from Jampason Elementary School. The results of such tests were as follows: level of preparedness for the resumption of face-to-face classes had 0.941 reliability value, burnout had 0.940 and work-life balance showed 0.943 reliability value.

Table 5. Reliability Statistics Results on Survey Questionnaire

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha Value	Description
Level of Preparedness for the Resumption of Face-to-Face Classes	0.941	Excellent
Job Burnout	0.940	Excellent
Work-life Balance	0.943	Excellent

Note: Cronbach's Alpha above 0.7 considered reliable
 ≥ 0.90, Excellent; 0.80-0.89, Good; 0.70-0.79, Acceptable; 0.60-0.69, Questionable; 0.50-0.59, Poor; ≤0.49, Unacceptable

Overall, the mean Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.941 which was described as excellent. For each variable the reliability test yielded Cronbach's alpha higher than 0.90 which was described as excellent. Based on the results, the instrument obtained an excellent internal consistency. Such results indicated that the instrument was reliable and was recommended for final administration.

Data Analysis

Upon retrieval of the accomplished questionnaires, responses were checked for accuracy and completeness. On the analysis of the data, descriptive and correlational statistical tools were used. Data were organized according to research problems. Appropriate statistical software was used to aid data analysis.

The mean and standard deviation were used to describe their level of preparedness for the resumption of face-to-face classes, job burnout and work-life balance. Pearson's product-moment correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' level of preparedness and their work-life balance and between respondents' job burnout during resumption of face-to-face classes and their work-life balance. The scale for quantitative and qualitative description or interpretation of mean scores, particularly of the teacher respondents' level of preparedness, job burnout, and work-life balance were given in Table 6, Table 7, and Table 8, respectively.

Table 6. Qualitative Description of the Respondents' Level of Preparedness for the Resumption of Face-to-Face Classes Mean Scores

Code	Limit	Qualitative Description / Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Very High Level of Preparedness
4	3.41-4.20	High Level of Preparedness
3	2.61-3.40	Moderate Level of Preparedness
2	1.81-2.60	Low Level of Preparedness
1	1.00-1.80	Very Low Level of Preparedness

Table 7. Qualitative Description of the Respondents' Job Burnout Mean Scores

Code	Limit	Qualitative Description / Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Very High Job Burnout
4	3.41-4.20	High Job Burnout
3	2.61-3.40	Moderate Job Burnout
2	1.81-2.60	Low Job Burnout
1	1.00-1.80	Very Low Job Burnout

Table 8. Qualitative Description of the Respondents' Work-life Balance Mean Scores

Code	Limit	Qualitative Description / Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Very High Work-life Balance
4	3.41-4.20	High Work-life Balance
3	2.61-3.40	Moderate Work-life Balance
2	1.81-2.60	Low Work-life Balance
1	1.00-1.80	Very Low Work-life Balance

Ethical Considerations

In conducting this study, the appropriate research behaviors were observed. Participation in the research was optional, and respondents might withdraw at any moment without obligation. Any physical or emotional discomfort towards certain subjects was also taken into consideration. Their voluntary decision to participate in the study was sought using SPC Free Prior Informed Consent Form.

In order for the respondents to thoroughly analyze their viewpoints on their degree of readiness, job burnout, and work-life balance, the researcher gave them enough time to complete the questionnaire. Information from the responders was kept private to preserve its confidentiality. In compliance with Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, students' names, the name of the

school they attended, and their identities were all be kept private in order to preserve their anonymity.

In accordance with American Psychological Association (APA) reference guidelines, the proper acknowledgment of each author whose work was used in the research shall be credited. The researcher did not fabricate data or outcomes and avoided plagiarism. There was no conflict of interest throughout the course of the research discussion. Consequently, the ethical aspects of research were scrupulously adhered to throughout the entirety of this study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussions in the study, categorized along themes to address the research questions, namely: respondent's level of preparedness, job burnout, work-life balance, relationship between level of preparedness and work-life balance, and relationship of job burnout and work-life balance during the resumption of face-to-face classes.

Level Of Respondents' Preparedness For The Resumption Of Face-To-Face Classes

The level of preparedness in the study referred to the overall readiness of respondents in managing and ensuring a safe and effective resumption of face-to-face classes. Four constructs constituted as its indicators namely: managing classroom operation, focusing on teaching and learning, well-being and protection, and classroom-community coordination.

Managing Classroom Operation

Managing classroom operation included the establishment of mechanisms to ensure compliance with health protocols and protective measures, the mobilization of resources and support from community stakeholders, and the implementation of safe entrance and exit and crowd management measures. The following were the components of controlling classroom operations: a. enlisting the aid of community stakeholders to provide resources and assistance in order to achieve health and safety procedure criteria, b. putting in place safeguards inside the classroom to guarantee that students' COVID-19 transmission is as little as possible, and c. implementing crowd control procedures, safe entry and departure points for the students. d. putting in place systems to ensure that health protocols and protective measures are observed, as well as visible and understandable signs. and e. putting in place contact tracing mechanisms for everyone who comes onto the school grounds. The level of preparedness for managing classroom operation was measured using a Likert scale with a score range of 1 to 5, with 1 indicating a very low level and 5 indicating a very high level. The mean scores and standard deviations were calculated for each item, as well as for the total measure. The mean scores indicated the average level of preparedness of the respondents, while the standard deviations provide a measure of variability in their responses.

Table 9. *Level of Preparedness in Managing Classroom Operation*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I established mechanisms inside the classroom to ensure minimal to zero COVID-19 transmission of the learners.	4.26±.80	High Level of Preparedness
I had set up clear and easy-to-understand signages, and mechanisms to strengthen observance of health protocols and protective measures.	4.23±.87	High Level of Preparedness
I established safe entrance and exit, and crowd management measures for the learners.	4.22±.88	High Level of Preparedness
I mobilized resources and support from community stakeholders to meet standards of the health and safety protocols.	4.06±.79	High Level of Preparedness
I established contact tracing procedures for all those who enter the classroom premises.	3.96±.96	High Level of Preparedness
Total Measure	4.15±.75	High Level of Preparedness

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level of Preparedness; 1.50-2.49, Low Level of Preparedness; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level of Preparedness; 3.50-4.49, High Level of Preparedness; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level of Preparedness

Table 9 provides the results on the level of respondents' preparedness during the resumption of face-to-face classes in terms of managing classroom operations. Based on the data in Table 9, the respondents assessed as high level on their preparedness for managing classroom operations during the resumption of face-to-face classes. The mean scores ranged from 3.96 to 4.26, with a total measure mean of 4.15.

Managing classroom operations posted varying levels of high preparedness. The item with the highest mean score was "I established mechanisms inside the classroom to ensure minimal to zero COVID-19 transmission of the learners" (M=4.26, SD=.80), indicating that the respondents were highly prepared in setting up safety measures inside the classroom to prevent COVID-19 transmission.

The next higher levels of preparedness which the respondents rated were on the items "I had set up clear and easy-to-understand signages, and mechanisms to strengthen observance of health protocols and protective measures" (M=4.23, SD=.87), and "I established safe entrance and exit, and crowd management measures for the learners." (M=4.22, SD=.88).

The item with the lowest mean score was "I established contact tracing procedures for all those who enter the classroom premises" (M=3.96, SD=.96). While the score was relatively high, it suggested that respondents might still need to improve their contact tracing procedures to ensure better management of the classroom operation during the resumption of face-to-face classes.

The findings of the study were consistent with Liu et al.'s (2021) earlier research that has tackled the importance of being well-prepared for the administration of face-to-face classes during the COVID-19 pandemic. With respect to dealing with the obstacles posed by the pandemic, Liu et al. (2021) found that teachers who felt supported and prepared for the challenges were less likely to experience

burnout and had higher levels of work-life balance. The study by Sun et al. (2021), which expanded on the physical aspect of classroom management, emphasized the importance of creating safety restrictions within the classroom, such as ventilation systems and physical distance guidelines, to reduce the spread of COVID-19.

Nevertheless, despite the respondents' typically high level of preparedness, it was important to consider the fluctuations in that level, as shown by the standard deviations. This suggested that the levels of readiness among the teacher responders varied, and that some of them could need additional assistance in some areas. For instance, enhancing contact tracing methods might be an area in which teachers required greater training or resources. This was evident in the lowest mean score that such an item obtained.

The data shown in Table 9 brought to light the significance of being well-prepared for the managing the resumption of in-person classes during the pandemic. Because they were more ready to manage the challenges and hazards connected with the pandemic, teachers who perceived that they were well-prepared and supported were more likely to have a better work-life balance and fewer levels of burnout.

Focusing on Teaching and Learning

The level of respondents' preparedness for focusing on teaching and learning during the resumption of face-to-face classes referred to the readiness of teachers in providing quality education to their students amidst the challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. The availability of adequate learning resources, access to teacher's guides or manuals, scheduling learning remediation or intervention, maintaining class size and physical distance, and offering a learning and development support plan were the factors used to gauge the level of preparedness for focusing on teaching and learning. The first indication assessed the teacher's capacity to supply the required reading materials for in-person lessons. This featured study guides, workbooks, and other extracurricular learning resources. The second indication assessed whether the teacher had access to a manual or teacher's guide on grade levels and subject matter to assist in their instruction. The third indicator measured the teacher's ability to schedule learning remediation or intervention as part of the regular class schedule and daily teaching time. The fourth indicator assessed whether the teacher could maintain class size and physical distancing in accordance with health and safety protocols. Finally, the fifth indicator measured the teacher's ability to provide learning and development support plans to improve the quality of basic education services.

Table 10 presents the results on the level of respondents' preparedness during the resumption of face-to-face classes in terms of focusing on teaching and learning. As shown in such Table, the respondents reported a high level of preparedness for focusing on teaching and learning during the resumption of face-to-face classes (total mean = 4.18), with the mean scores ranging from 3.83 to 4.49.

Table 10. *Level of Preparedness for Focusing on Teaching and Learning*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I ensured that I have the Teacher's Guide/Teacher's Manual on specific grade level and learning area I am handling.	4.49±.76	High Level of Preparedness
I ensured that learning remediation/intervention is part of the regular class schedule and daily teaching time, for a minimum of one hour depending upon the needs of the learners.	4.31±.86	High Level of Preparedness
I secured sufficient supply of learning resources needed for the face-to-face classes.	4.19±.75	High Level of Preparedness
I provided an appropriate learning and development support plan in the delivery of better-quality basic education services.	4.10±.84	High Level of Preparedness
I ensured that the class size is in accordance with the number of learners in a classroom and required one-meter physical distancing.	3.83±.96	High Level of Preparedness
Total Measure	4.18±.70	High Level of Preparedness

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level of Preparedness; 1.50-2.49, Low Level of Preparedness; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level of Preparedness; 3.50-4.49, High Level of Preparedness; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level of Preparedness

Garnering the highest mean score of 4.49 and a standard deviation of 0.76 was the item "I ensured that I have the Teacher's Guide/Teacher's Manual on specific grade level and learning area I am handling", indicating a high level of preparedness. This suggested that the respondents saw to it that they acquired the necessary instructional materials to aid them in their teaching duties, which was essential for effective teaching and learning. Coming up next was the item on "I secured sufficient supply of learning resources needed for the face-to-face classes" with a mean of 4.19 and a standard deviation of 0.75, which also suggested a high level of preparedness. This implied that the respondents had taken the necessary steps to ensure that adequate supply of learning materials were readily available for their students to access for effective learning. Third in high mean score was "I ensured that learning remediation/intervention was part of the regular class schedule and daily teaching time, for a minimum of one hour depending upon the needs of the learners" with a mean of 4.31 and a standard deviation of 0.86, which also suggested a high level of preparedness. This indicated that the respondents had considered the needs of their students in terms of remediation and intervention and had made sure to include it in their regular teaching schedule. Remediation often entailed offering targeted teaching and practice to students to help them improve their skills in a certain area, such as reading comprehension, arithmetic problem solving, or writing. If a teacher noticed that some of their students were struggling with reading comprehension, remediation can be undertaken by providing additional reading materials at their appropriate reading level, guided reading sessions, or one-on-one tutoring to help them improve their comprehension skills. Intervention, on the other hand, was often focused on resolving larger learning gaps that might be impeding a student's overall academic success. It might entail giving pupils extra training and support to help them catch up on missed or misunderstood topics or abilities. If a teacher noticed that a group of students in their class were struggling with basic math concepts, an intervention might be

done by providing additional lessons, hands-on activities, or differentiated instruction to help these students filled in the gaps in their understanding.

The item “I provided an appropriate learning and development support plan in the delivery of better-quality basic education services” garnered the fourth highest mean at 4.10 and a standard deviation of 0.84, indicating a high level of preparedness. This showed that the respondents had taken the necessary steps to ensure that their teaching strategies were aligned with the learning goals and objectives of their students.

Finally, the item with the lowest mean score was “I ensured that the class size was in accordance with the required number of learners in a classroom and required one-meter physical distancing” with a mean of 3.83 and a standard deviation of 0.96, which was also a high level of preparedness. This implied that the respondents had made sure that they complied with the safety protocols mandated by the government, although there might have been certain challenges in ensuring that physical distancing was maintained in the classroom.

Relating such findings to that of earlier research, a high degree of preparedness among teachers was observed in terms of their ability to concentrate on instruction and student progress when regular face-to-face sessions resumed. As revealed in the study conducted by Hong et al. (2021), teachers who were provided with enough training and support were better equipped to offer effective teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. In another piece of research, De la Fuente et al. (2021) found that teachers who had access to online professional development programs had a higher level of self-assurance with respect to the use of digital resources for teaching and learning. Preparedness in this context, might take the form of training and support and online professional development programs.

Moreover, it was essential for teachers to have access to the Teacher's Guide or the Teacher's Manual to ensure that they had all the relevant instructional resources. According to the Philippines Department of Education (2020), the Teacher's Guide/Teacher's Manual covered all the essential content and methodologies for presenting the curriculum. This information might be found in the manual. It gave teachers the right sequence of lessons, learning objectives, and suggested activities to guarantee that learning goals were reached. The importance of having a copy and using the Teacher's Guide or Teacher's Manual was also brought to light in the research conducted by Pineda et al. (2021), which uncovered that the Teacher's Guide assisted the teachers in planning their lectures in a way that was both successful and efficient.

Regarding the necessity to guarantee suitable class size and physical distancing measures, the World Health Organization (2020) had advised keeping a distance of at least one meter between persons to decrease the risk of COVID-19 transmission. This recommendation was made to explain why proper class size and physical distancing measures had been required. Studies had indicated that classrooms that were too packed might increase the risk of disease transmission (Guan et al., 2020; Viner et al., 2020). Correspondingly, it was essential that educational institutions put in place the necessary precautions to ensure adequate levels of class size and physical separation.

On the whole, the result suggested that the respondents were well-prepared for focusing on teaching and learning during the resumption of face-to-face classes. The high mean scores across all items indicated that they had taken measures to secure sufficient learning resources, to ensure that learning remediation was part of the regular class schedule, and to provide appropriate learning and development support plans.

Well-being and Protection

Well-being and protection referred to the measures that ensured the health and safety of learners, teachers, and school personnel during the resumption of face-to-face classes. It involved providing a safe and secure environment for learning, for implementing measures to prevent the spread of COVID-19. Also, it ensured the availability of basic mental health and psychosocial support. The items on well-being and protection in the study included: a. availability of sanitation and disinfection materials in strategic classroom locations, b. development of strategies to prevent COVID-19, c. availability and maintenance of the provision of basic mental health and psychosocial support, as well as guidance and counselling services to learners, d. development of a reporting system requiring parents to report to the school if their children were experiencing flu-like symptoms, and e. development of learning strategies to cater to the needs of marginalized learners, such as modules in Braille, mother-tongue languages, and usage of Filipino sign language. As with other indicators, these items were measured using a five-point Likert scale.

Posted in Table 11 are the results on the level of respondents' preparedness during the resumption of face-to-face classes in terms of well-being and protection. Overall, a high level of preparedness in ensuring the well-being and protection of learners during the resumption of face-to-face classes was reported, with a mean score of 4.11 and a standard deviation of ± 0.69 .

Rated the highest mean score of 4.2 and a standard deviation of .78 was the item "I developed a reporting system requiring parents to report to the school if their children were experiencing flu-like symptoms". This indicated that the respondents were highly prepared in terms of ensuring that the school was informed if any of their students were showing flu-like symptoms. This measure was crucial in preventing the spread of diseases, such as COVID-19, within the school community. Second in rank was the item "I ensured the availability of sanitation and disinfection materials in strategic classroom locations," with a mean score of 4.26, and a standard deviation of .87. This result suggested that the respondents were highly prepared in terms of providing sanitation and disinfection materials in

classrooms. This measure was crucial in maintaining a safe and healthy learning environment for students and teachers. Developing strategies to prevent COVID-19 obtained the third highest with a mean score at 4.19, and a standard deviation of .84. This result indicated that the respondents were highly prepared to craft strategies to prevent the spread of COVID-19 within the school community. This measure included implementing safety protocols, such as social distancing, wearing face masks, and regular handwashing, among others. Following next was the item "I ensured availability and maintained the provision of basic mental health and psychosocial support, as well as guidance and counseling services to learners," with a mean score of 4.09, and a standard deviation of .76. This result suggested that the respondents were highly prepared to provide basic mental health and psychosocial support to learners. This measure was essential in addressing the mental health and psychosocial needs of students, especially during these challenging times.

Table 11. *Level of Preparedness for Well-being and Protection*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I developed a reporting system requiring parents to report to the school if their children are experiencing flu-like symptoms.	4.27±.78	High Level of Preparedness
I ensured the availability of sanitation and disinfection materials in strategic classroom locations.	4.26±.87	High Level of Preparedness
I developed strategies to prevent COVID- 19.	4.19±.84	High Level of Preparedness
I ensured availability and maintained the provision of basic mental health and psychosocial support, as well as guidance and counselling services to learners.	4.09±.76	High Level of Preparedness
I developed learning strategies to cater the needs of the marginalized learners, such as modules in Braille, mother-tongue languages, and usage of Filipino Sign Language.	3.75±1.11	High Level of Preparedness
Total Measure	4.11±.69	High Level of Preparedness

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level of Preparedness; 1.50-2.49, Low Level of Preparedness; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level of Preparedness; 3.50-4.49, High Level of Preparedness; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level of Preparedness

Assessed with the lowest mean score was the item "I developed learning strategies to cater to the needs of marginalized learners, such as modules in Braille, mother-tongue languages, and the usage of Filipino sign language," with a mean score of 3.75, and a standard deviation of 1.11. Although, the mean score was still within the high-level range, it suggested that there was a need for improvement in terms of developing learning strategies that catered to the needs of marginalized learners. This measure was crucial to ensuring that all students, regardless of their background or abilities, had access to quality education.

Throughout the time of the pandemic, it had been underscored in several studies how important it was to keep the learning environment clean and risk-free. For instance, a study that was conducted in Bangladesh by Hossain and colleagues (2021) discovered that establishing good sanitation and hygiene standards in schools was essential to avoiding the spread of COVID-19. In India, Patra and Mishra (2021) conducted another study that highlighted the significance of ensuring that schools had sufficient sanitation facilities in order to protect the health and safety of students.

Other research underlined the necessity to develop strategies to meet the needs of underprivileged students, such as those with impairments. According to Kurniawan et al.'s (2020) research in Indonesia, pupils with disabilities have been disproportionately affected negatively by the COVID-19 epidemic. To ensure that these pupils could continue their education in this atmosphere, teachers had to come up with original techniques. In a same spirit, Khan and Shahzad's study from Pakistan in 2021 underlined the importance of making sure that during the epidemic, children with impairments had access to an inclusive school.

Hence, the result suggested that the respondents were well-prepared for ensuring the well-being and protection of learners during the resumption of face-to-face classes. The high mean scores across most items indicated that they had taken measures to ensure the availability of sanitation and disinfection materials, develop strategies to prevent COVID-19, and provide basic mental health and psychosocial support. However, the lower score for catering to the needs of marginalized learners suggested that more attention might need to be given to this area of preparedness.

In summary, the findings of the study suggested that the respondents were highly prepared for their own well-being and protection during the resumption of face-to-face classes. The study highlighted the importance of providing sanitation and disinfection materials, developing strategies to prevent COVID-19, providing mental health and psychosocial support to learners, and developing learning strategies that catered to the needs of marginalized learners. These measures were critical to ensuring a safe, healthy, and inclusive learning environment for all students and teachers.

Classroom-Community Coordination

Classroom-community coordination referred to the level of preparedness of teachers and school personnel in coordinating with the community, particularly with the local government units and parents/guardians, in ensuring the safety and well-being of students during the resumption of face-to-face classes. The indicators of classroom-community coordination in the study were as follows: a. developing a plan for coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team (BHERT) in ensuring that protocols were observed properly, b. identifying a designated waiting area with strict observation of physical distancing for parents/guardians/chaperones, c. coordinating with their respective local government units the implementation of routine school-based immunization (SBI) and other school health-related services, d. developing intensive health promotion campaign activities/supportive-policies to maintain optimal health-seeking behavior of learners, and e. securing written consent from the

parents/guardians of learners who would participate in the face-to-face classes. To measure the level of respondents' preparedness for classroom-community coordination, the study used a five-point Likert scale survey questionnaire.

Table 12. *Level of Preparedness for Classroom-Community Coordination*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I secured written consent from the parents/guardians of learners who will participate in the face-to-face classes.	4.37±.87	High Level of Preparedness
I identified a designated waiting area with strict observation of physical distancing for parents/ guardians/ chaperones.	4.17±.81	High Level of Preparedness
I developed intensive health promotion campaign activities/supportive-policies to maintain optimal health-seeking behavior of learners.	4.10±.83	High Level of Preparedness
I developed a plan for coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team (BHERT) in ensuring that protocols are observed properly.	3.95±.79	High Level of Preparedness
I coordinated with their respective local government units the implementation of routine school-based immunization (SBI) and other school health-related services.	3.93±.91	High Level of Preparedness
Total Measure	4.10±.72	High Level of Preparedness

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level of Preparedness; 1.50-2.49, Low Level of Preparedness; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level of Preparedness; 3.50-4.49, High Level of Preparedness; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level of Preparedness

Generally, respondents had a high-level preparedness for classroom-community coordination during the resumption of face-to-face classes with an overall mean score of 4.10. Looking at each item more closely, the highest level of preparedness, with a mean score of 4.37 and a standard deviation of 0.87, was securing written consent from parents/guardians of learners who would participate in the face-to-face classes. Coming up next, with a mean score of 4.17 and a standard deviation of 0.81, was identifying a designated waiting area with strict observance of physical distancing for parents/guardians/chaperones. Developing intensive health promotion campaign activities/supportive-policies to maintain optimal health-seeking behavior of learners obtained the third highest level of preparedness, with a mean score of 4.10 and a standard deviation of 0.83. This was followed by developing a plan for coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team (BHERT) in ensuring that protocols were observed properly, with a mean score of 3.95 and a standard deviation of 0.79. The lowest level of preparedness, with a mean score of 3.93 and a standard deviation of 0.91, was coordinating with their respective local government units the implementation of routine school-based immunization (SBI) and other school health-related services.

The study found that the respondents had a high level of preparedness for classroom-community coordination during the resumption of face-to-face classes, with a total mean score of 4.10±0.72. The highest level of preparedness was in securing written consent from the parents/guardians of learners who would participate in face-to-face classes, with a mean score of 4.37±0.87. This indicated that the respondents recognized the importance of obtaining written consent from parents or guardians before allowing their children to attend face-to-face classes. This finding was consistent with the study by Madi and Hamdan (2019) which showed that obtaining parental consent was crucial in ensuring the safety of children in school.

The next highest level of preparedness was in identifying a designated waiting area with strict observation of physical distancing for parents/guardians/chaperones, with a mean score of 4.17±0.81. This highlighted the importance of implementing measures to ensure physical distancing and reduce the risk of transmission of infectious diseases. This finding was aligned with the guideline of the World Health Organization (WHO) which recommended maintaining physical distancing in schools as a key strategy to prevent the spread of COVID-19 (WHO, 2021).

The third highest level of preparedness was in developing intensive health promotion campaign activities/supportive-policies to maintain optimal health-seeking behavior of learners, with a mean score of 4.10±0.83. This emphasized the need to promote health-seeking behaviors among learners to prevent the spread of infectious diseases. This finding agreed with the recommendation of the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) which highlighted the importance of promoting healthy behaviors in schools to prevent the spread of infectious diseases (CDC, 2021).

The fourth highest level of preparedness was in developing a plan for coordination with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU) or the Barangay Health Emergency Response Team (BHERT) in ensuring that protocols were observed properly, with a mean score of 3.95±0.79. This highlighted the importance of coordination between the school and the local government unit to ensure that proper health protocols were implemented. This finding supported with the recommendation of the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) which emphasized the need for coordination between the school and the local government unit in ensuring the safety of learners (DepEd, 2021).

The lowest level of preparedness was in coordinating with their respective local government units in the implementation of routine school-based immunization (SBI) and other school health-related services, with a mean score of 3.93±0.91. This indicated that the respondents might need to improve their efforts in coordinating with the local government units in implementing routine school-based immunization and other health-related services. This finding resonated with the recommendation of the WHO which emphasized the importance of routine immunization in schools to prevent the spread of infectious diseases (WHO, 2021).

To sum up, the findings of the study suggested that the respondents had a generally high level of preparedness for classroom-community coordination during the resumption of face-to-face classes. However, there was still room for improvement in some areas, particularly in coordinating with the local government unit in implementing routine immunization and other health-related services. The study highlighted the importance of coordination between the schools and the local government units in ensuring the safety and well-being of learners during the resumption of face-to-face classes.

Consolidated Results on Level of Preparedness

The COVID-19 epidemic had a significant impact on the education industry, forcing colleges and universities to switch to online or mixed learning environments in order to maintain social segregation policies. A growing number of people were interested in starting face-to-face classes again as vaccines were more widely available. However, there were worries about how ready educators and schools were to guarantee the community's and students' safety during the shift. The findings of the respondents' preparedness for managing classroom operations, concentrating on teaching and learning, maintaining the safety and well-being of students, and working with the community when face-to-face classes resumed were compiled in Table 10. The results provided insights into the overall level of preparedness of the respondents and highlighted the areas where further improvements might have been necessary to ensure a smooth and safe transition back to face-to-face classes.

Table 13. Consolidated Results on the Level of Preparedness by Indicator

Indicator	Mean \pm SD	Description
Managing Classroom Operation	4.15 \pm .75	High Level of Preparedness
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	4.18 \pm .70	High Level of Preparedness
Well-being and Protection	4.11 \pm .69	High Level of Preparedness
Classroom-Community Coordination	4.10 \pm .72	High Level of Preparedness
Total Measure	4.14 \pm .66	High Level of Preparedness

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level of Preparedness; 1.50-2.49, Low Level of Preparedness; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level of Preparedness; 3.50-4.49, High Level of Preparedness; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level of Preparedness

Based on the consolidated results on the level of preparedness for the resumption of face-to-face classes, the respondents demonstrated a high level of preparedness in managing classroom operations, focusing on teaching and learning, ensuring the well-being and protection of students, and coordinating with the community with overall mean of 4.14, and standard deviation of .66.

The highest mean score was observed in the indicator "focusing on teaching and learning" ($M=4.18$, $SD=0.70$), indicating that the respondents had high preparedness levels in ensuring that their teaching approaches were effective in promoting students' learning outcomes. This finding was crucial to ensuring that the transition to face-to-face classes was successful, as the quality of teaching and learning was a key determinant of student success. The next highest mean score was noted in the indicator "managing classroom operation" ($M=4.15$, $SD=.75$), which suggested that the respondents had high preparedness level in managing the classroom operations. This included managing the physical environment, maintaining a safe and conducive learning space, and ensuring that the resources needed for teaching and learning were available. The third-highest mean score was observed in the item "well-being and protection" ($M=4.11$, $SD=0.69$), indicating that the respondents had high preparedness levels in ensuring the well-being and protection of students. This consisted of implementing health and safety protocols such as hand washing, wearing face masks, and social distancing, as well as addressing the students' physical, emotional, and mental health needs. Lastly, the item "classroom-community coordination" ($M=4.10$, $SD=0.72$), implying that the respondents had high preparedness levels in coordinating with the community to ensure a smooth and safe transition to face-to-face classes. This included engaging with parents, local government units, and other stakeholders to address any concerns and ensure that everyone was working together to support the students' education.

Focusing on teaching and learning posted the highest mean score among all indicators, suggesting that the respondents were well-prepared to prioritize teaching and learning during the transition back to face-to-face classes. This result was consistent with the existing literature which highlighted the importance of maintaining the quality of education during the transition (Hwang & Teoh, 2021; Mavropoulou & Mavropoulos, 2021). Ensuring the quality of education was particularly important as students might have experienced disruptions in their learning during the pandemic.

The familiarity of teachers with the conventional face-to-face classes, when controlling classroom operations was a common practice, might be responsible for the high degree of preparedness in managing classroom operations. In order to create an effective learning environment, previous research had emphasized the significance of controlling classroom operations, which included elements including classroom design, seating arrangements, and student behavior management (Kong, 2014; Zanakis et al., 2017).

The high level of preparedness in the well-being and protection indicator was essential to ensuring the safety and health of students, teachers, and the community. Previous research had emphasized the importance of ensuring student well-being and protection, particularly during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Rahman et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2021). The high level of preparedness in this indicator might be attributed to the implementation of strict health and safety protocols, such as social distancing measures, regular sanitation, and the provision of personal protective equipment.

Lastly, the classroom-community coordination indicator garnered a high mean score, indicating that the respondents were well-prepared to coordinate with the community during the transition back to face-to-face classes. To achieve a smooth transition and

enhance the safety and wellbeing of students and the community, coordination with the community was essential (Hirvonen & Kiviranta, 2021; Valdez et al., 2021). To create and implement safety standards and emergency plans, it might be necessary to work with local health authorities, parents, and other stakeholders.

In summary, the results of the survey demonstrated a high level of preparedness among the respondents in all indicators related to the resumption of face-to-face classes. These findings were consistent with previous studies that highlighted the importance of managing classroom operations, prioritizing teaching and learning, ensuring well-being and protection, and coordinating with the community during the transition. The results provided insights for teachers, policymakers, and stakeholders in improving and implementing effective strategies for a smooth and safe transition back to face-to-face classes.

Level Of Respondents' Job Burnout During The Resumption Of Face-To-Face Classes

Job burnout referred to a psychological syndrome that resulted from chronic stress in the workplace. It had three characteristics: diminished personal accomplishment, depersonalization, and emotional weariness. Depersonalization was the emergence of unfavorable, pessimistic attitudes and feelings about one's job and clients, whereas emotional exhaustion was the experience of being emotionally drained and exhausted from work. Reduced personal accomplishment referred to a drop in one's assessment of their professional achievements.

In this study, job burnout was measured using the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) for teachers, a widely used questionnaire designed to assess job burnout in teaching profession. The MBI consisted of three indicators that corresponded to the three dimensions of burnout. The respondents were asked to rate their experiences on each indicator using a five-point Likert scale. For the total measure, the scale ranges from 1.00-1.49 as "very low", 1.50-2.49 as "low", 2.50-3.49 as "moderate", 3.50-4.49 as "high", and 4.50-5.00 as "very high".

Emotional Exhaustion

Emotional exhaustion referred to the feeling of being emotionally drained or depleted due to excessive work demands and stressors. In this study, emotional exhaustion was measured in terms of the following items: a. I feel emotionally drained from my work, b. I feel used up at the end of the workday, c. I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and must face another day on the job, d. working with people all day was really a strain for me, e. I feel burned out from my work, f. I feel frustrated by my job, g. I feel I'm working too hard on my job, h. Working with people directly puts too much stress on me, and h. I feel like I'm at the end of my rope.

Table 14. *Level of Emotional Exhaustion*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I feel used up at the end of the workday.	2.69±1.74	Moderate Emotional Exhaustion
I feel emotionally drained from my work.	2.55±1.62	Moderate Emotional Exhaustion
I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and have to face another day on the job.	2.27±1.76	Low Emotional Exhaustion
I feel burned out from my work.	1.87±1.63	Low Emotional Exhaustion
I feel I'm working too hard on my job.	1.74±1.70	Low Emotional Exhaustion
Working with people all day is really a strain for me.	1.38±1.53	Very Low Emotional Exhaustion
Working with people directly puts too much stress on me.	1.19±1.54	Very Low Emotional Exhaustion
I feel frustrated by my job.	1.09±1.43	Very Low Emotional Exhaustion
I feel like I'm at the end of my rope.	1.01±1.48	Very Low Emotional Exhaustion
Total Measure	1.75±1.34	Low

Legend: 0.00-0.48, Never Emotionally Exhausted; 0.50-1.49, Very Low Emotional Exhaustion; 1.50-2.49, Low Emotional Exhaustion; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Emotional Exhaustion; 3.50-4.49, High Emotional Exhaustion; 4.50-5.00, Very High Emotional Exhaustion

As shown in Table 14, the mean scores ranged from 1.01 to 2.69, with a total measure mean score of 1.75, described as low level of emotional exhaustion. An overall standard deviation of 1.75, indicated the average degree of variation or dispersion around the mean score for each indicator.

Ranking the mean scores from the highest, the highest was garnered by the item "I feel used up at the end of the workday," (M=2.69, SD=1.74) indicating a moderate level of emotional exhaustion. This item referred to the feeling of being physically and emotionally depleted at the end of the workday. Coming next was the item "I feel emotionally drained from my work," (M=2.55, SD=1.62) also indicating a moderate level of emotional exhaustion. This item referred to the feeling of being emotionally exhausted and depleted from work demands. The next higher item was "I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and have to face another day on the job," (M=2.27, SD=1.76) indicating a low level of emotional exhaustion. This item referred to the feeling of physical and emotional fatigue upon waking up and anticipating the demands of the workday. The fourth higher item was "I feel burned out from my work," (M=1.87, SD=1.63) indicating a low level of emotional exhaustion. This item referred to the feeling of being emotionally exhausted and disconnected from work. The rest of the items obtained similarly low mean scores indicating low level of emotional exhaustion. These included the following in descending order: a) "I feel I'm working too hard on my job," (M=1.74, SD=1.70); b) "Working with people all day is really a strain for me," (M=1.38, SD=1.53); c) "Working with people directly puts too much stress on me," (M=1.19, SD=1.54); d) "I feel frustrated with my job," (M=1.09, SD=1.43); and e) "I feel like I'm at the end of my rope," (M=1.01, SD=1.48) indicating a very low level of emotional exhaustion. This item referred to the feeling of being at one's limit or breaking point.

The finding on moderate level of emotional exhaustion aligned with that of previous studies which found that emotional exhaustion

was common among teachers, particularly those who worked in high-stress environments (Leiter & Maslach, 2018; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2018).

According to Maslach, Schaufeli, and Leiter (2017), emotional exhaustion is defined by emotions of exhaustion, depletion, and a lack of energy, which can impair job performance and increase absenteeism and turnover. Similar to how Kyriacou, Zhang, and Klassen (2018) found that emotional weariness was a widespread issue among instructors, particularly those who worked with underprivileged pupils. These findings were converging. Workload, work-family conflict, and unfavorable working conditions were just a few of the things that could lead to emotional tiredness (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2018).

On the other hand, feeling fatigued when getting up in the morning and had to face another day on the job obtained a relatively low mean score, which meant a low level of emotional exhaustion. This was a positive finding, as fatigue could be a precursor to emotional exhaustion and could negatively impact job performance (Bakker, Demerouti, & Sanz-Vergel, 2014).

The items "Working with people all day is really a strain for me" and "Working with people directly puts too much stress on me" had the lowest mean scores ($M=1.38$, $SD=1.53$ and $M=1.19$, $SD=1.54$, respectively), indicating a very low level of emotional exhaustion. This was consistent with previous research that had found working with people to be a source of social support and could buffer the negative effects of stress (Bakker et al., 2014; Kyriacou, 2018).

A rundown of the results showed that emotional exhaustion was not quite an issue among teacher respondents during the resumption of face-to-face classes, although they experienced a moderate level of which particularly in terms of being used up at the end of the workday. Overall, the findings showed that stress and burnout among teachers during the start of face-to-face classes were caused by a variety of variables. The quantity of work teachers had to do, the lack of support they received, and disruptive pupils were just a few of the factors that had been linked to teacher burnout in the past (Kyriacou, 2001; Maslach & Leiter, 1997). According to the current analysis, instructors might have had more strain and stress due to the additional responsibilities of enforcing health and safety rules during the pandemic (Kim & Asbury, 2020). These findings underscored the importance of addressing the root causes of emotional exhaustion, such as workload and poor working conditions, to promote teacher well-being and improve job performance.

That most of the items were assessed in varying degrees of low to very low emotional exhaustion suggested that generally, the teacher respondents experienced only a negligible level of emotional exhaustion which could be considered reasonable or normal. One factor that might help explain away such low level of emotional exhaustion could be the high level of preparedness for managing classroom operation, focusing on teaching and learning, well-being and protection, and classroom-community coordination, as earlier presented and discussed.

Depersonalization

Depersonalization generally referred to a psychological state in which an individual became detached from others and began to view them as objects rather than individuals with emotions and feelings. In the context of the study, depersonalization referred to teachers' tendency to view their students as impersonal objects and to become emotionally detached from them. This was measured using a five-point scale along five items that tapped into different aspects of this construct. These items were: a. I feel I treat some students as if they were impersonal objects, b. I've become more callous toward people since I took this job, c. I worry that this job is hardening me emotionally, d. I don't really care what happens to some students, and e. I feel students blame me for some of their problems.

Taken together, the total measure mean score for depersonalization was 0.48, indicating a never level of depersonalization. This suggested that the respondents in this study did not experience substantial levels of depersonalization during the resumption of face-to-face classes.

Table 15. *Level of Depersonalization*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I don't really care what happens to some students.	.24±.72	Never Depersonalized
I feel students blame me for some of their problems.	.33±.74	Never Depersonalized
I've become more callous toward people since I took this job.	.48±.99	Never Depersonalized
I feel I treat some students as if they were impersonal objects.	.63±1.25	Very Low Depersonalization
I worry that this job is hardening me emotionally.	.74±1.25	Very Low Depersonalization
Total Measure	.48±.83	Never

Legend: 0.00-0.49, Never Depersonalized; 0.50-1.49, Very Low Depersonalization; 1.50-2.49, Low Depersonalization; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Depersonalization; 3.50-4.49, High Depersonalization; 4.50-5.00, Very High Depersonalization

Of the five indicator items with the highest mean score was obtained by the item "I worried that this job was hardening me emotionally" with a mean score of 0.74 and a standard deviation of 1.25, indicating a very low level of depersonalization. This item reflected the negligible emotional exhaustion that teachers experienced perhaps because of their job demands. This result was consistent with existing literature that suggested that teachers were prone to emotional exhaustion due to the demands of their job (Maslach & Leiter, 2017). Emotional exhaustion was viewed a component of burnout, which could lead to depersonalization (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). Teachers who worried that their job was making them insensitive to the concerns of others might have experienced some feelings of burnout or exhaustion, but they still generally saw their students as people rather than objects. The item "I felt I treated some students as if they were impersonal objects" garnered a mean score of 0.63 and a standard deviation of 1.25, indicating a very low level of

depersonalization. This item reflected the tendency of teachers to see some students as objects rather than as human beings. This could be due to their feelings of frustration with students or with the demands of the job in general. This finding was consistent with research of Klassen and Chiu (2010) which found that teachers generally see their students as individuals.

Looking further into the data in Table 12, most of the items registered very low mean scores come on indicating no experience or feeling of depersonalization apple or never depersonalized among the teacher respondents, as reflected in the following items: a) "I don't really care what happens to some students." (M=.24); b) "I feel students blame me for some of their problems." (M=.33) and c) "I've become more callous toward people since I took this job." (M=.48). That the respondents were never depersonalized along these areas of relationship with their students suggested that they were sensitive to the needs and concerns of their students, being responsible teachers. Thus, their students were likewise responsible for their problems, instead of projecting these to their teachers.

Based on the findings of previously published material, it was possible to ascribe the respondents' lack of experiencing depersonalization to a number of interrelated reasons. For instance, Kyriakon (2011) stressed how much teachers cared about and appreciated their students. Due to this, their teachers did not typically view their students as antagonistic or accusatory (Meece & Holt, 1993). Moreover, Dweck and Leggett (1988) viewed that teachers were interested in the academic growth of their students.

The non-occurrence of substantial level of depersonalization could be due to various other factors, such as the length of time that the respondents had been teaching, the support they received from their colleagues and superiors, or the resilience of the respondents themselves.

In a study by Klassen et al. (2019), it was found that teacher resilience was positively associated with job satisfaction and negatively associated with emotional exhaustion. This suggested that teachers who were more resilient were better able to cope with the demands of their job. This might reduce the likelihood of experiencing depersonalization. Additionally, it can be explained by the nature of the teaching profession. According to Maslach and Leiter (2016), teaching was a caring profession that required intimate ties with pupils on a personal level. Being in constant contact with pupils and more inclined to see them as people than as objects might make it more difficult for teachers to become depersonalized.

In conclusion, the findings of the current study showed that the respondents did not significantly experience degrees of depersonalization, even though the return to face-to-face classrooms might have brought new obstacles for teachers. However, it was important for educators and policymakers to continue to monitor the well-being of teachers, as depersonalization and other components of burnout could have negative consequences for both teachers and students. As the study by Chan and Hsu (2021) exploring the relationship between teacher burnout and student outcomes in secondary schools in Hong Kong found emotional exhaustion. Thus, a key component of burnout was negatively associated with student engagement and achievement. The finding suggested that teacher burnout, which included depersonalization, could have negative consequences for students.

Reduced Personal Accomplishment

Reduced personal accomplishment was a component of burnout that referred to a teacher's perception of their lack of effectiveness in their job and a decreased sense of achievement or accomplishment. It was an important aspect of burnout as it might lead to feelings of helplessness, hopelessness, and a reduced commitment to teaching (Maslach & Leiter, 2017). Indicators of decreased personal accomplishment in this study included emotional difficulties, inability to solve problems effectively, bad influence on others, weariness, inability to create a relaxed environment, tension, and decreased personal accomplishment. These indications suggested that the respondents' perceived lack of effectiveness and performance was a result of challenges they faced at work. A five-item scale modified from the Maslach Burnout Inventory for Educators (MBI-ES) (Schaufeli, Leiter, Maslach, & Jackson, 1996) was used in this study to assess decreasing personal accomplishment. The items were rated on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (every day), with higher scores indicating higher levels of reduced personal accomplishment.

The total measure of 0.96 shown in Table 16 indicated a very low level of reduced personal accomplishment. This result suggested that the respondents did not perceive themselves as being ineffective in their job or as experiencing a decreased sense of level of accomplishment during the resumption of face-to-face classes. Such a very low level of personal accomplishment was reflected in six out of the eight items, while one item was rated never, and another item was scored low.

Table 16. *Level of Reduced Personal Accomplishment*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I feel usually exhausted at the end of a day's work	1.68±1.68	Low
I feel stressed after working closely with my students.	1.26±1.41	Very Low
I can hardly create a relaxed atmosphere with my students.	1.07±1.22	Very Low
I have difficulty understanding how my students feel about things.	.92±1.15	Very Low
I have accomplished less worthwhile things in this job.	.85±1.10	Very Low
In my work, I struggle with emotional problems with much difficulty.	.85±1.07	Very Low
I am ineffective in dealing with the problems of my students.	.64±.92	Very Low
I feel I'm negatively influencing other people's lives through my work.	.45±.90	Never
Total Measure	.96±.91	Very Low

Legend: 0.00-0.49, Never; 0.50-1.49, Very Low; 1.50-2.49, Low; 2.50-3.49, Moderate; 3.50-4.49, High; 4.50-5.00, Very High

The item with the highest mean was "I feel usually exhausted at the end of a day's work" with a mean of 1.68 and standard deviation of 1.68, which indicated a low level of reduced personal accomplishment. This suggested that the respondents might have experienced some amount of exhaustion at the amount of a day's work, but such a feeling of fatigue was not high enough to make them feel that their personal accomplishment had diminished. Their low feeling of fatigue might either be physical, mental or both. Except for the item on negatively influencing other people's lives through their work which yielded a mean score of .45 described as never experienced reduced personal accomplishment. The rest of the items were rated in varying levels of very low reduced personal accomplishment. These items included the following: a) "I feel stressed after working closely with my students" (M=1.26); b) "I can hardly create a relaxed atmosphere with my students" (M=1.07); c) "I have difficulty understanding how my students feel about things" (M=.92); d) "I have accomplished less worthwhile things in this job" (M=.85); e) "in my work I struggle with emotional problems with much difficulty" (M=.85); and f) "I am ineffective in dealing with the problems of my students" (M=.64). Looking at these results from the opposite side of the continuum, it could be inferred that in general, respondents did not feel stressed after working closely with their students. They had less difficulty creating a relaxed atmosphere with their students. They had less difficulty understanding their students' feelings about things come on they had accomplished more worthwhile things in their job. They had less difficulty struggling with their emotional problems, and they felt effective in dealing with the problems of their students.

The item with the highest mean was "I feel usually exhausted at the end of a day's work" (M=1.68, SD=1.68), which indicated a low level of reduced personal accomplishment. This suggested that the respondents might have experienced physical exhaustion due to the demands of face-to-face teaching, but they did not feel that their personal accomplishment had been reduced. This finding was consistent with existing literature that suggested that teaching could be a physically demanding job, particularly during face-to-face instruction (McLean & Connor, 2017).

The item with the second-highest mean was "I feel stressed after working closely with my students" with a mean of 1.26 ± 1.41 , which also indicated a very low level of reduced personal accomplishment. This suggested that the respondents might have experienced stress due to their interactions with students, but this stress did not necessarily translate to a reduced sense of personal accomplishment. This finding was consistent with the literature that suggested that stress was a common experience among teachers, particularly during face-to-face instruction (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017).

With a mean of 0.45 0.90, the response "I feel I'm negatively influencing other people's lives through my work", had the lowest mean and represented respondents' lack of awareness of this possibility. This indicated that the respondents felt positively about their teaching jobs and did not believe that their work was negatively affecting others. This result was in line with the research (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011), which claimed that teaching might be a fulfilling profession that allowed teachers to have a positive impact on the lives of their pupils.

One study that was supported by the finding on low reduced personal accomplishment among teachers was a study conducted by Hakanen, Bakker, and Schaufeli (2006). The study found that teachers who reported higher levels of personal accomplishment had lower levels of burnout, which was a state of physical and emotional exhaustion. The study also found that personal accomplishment was positively related to job satisfaction and negatively related to intentions to quit. These findings suggested that teachers who had a high sense of personal accomplishment were more likely to be satisfied with their job and less likely to experience burnout or leave their job.

Another study by Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2017) found that teachers who had a strong sense of personal accomplishment were less likely to experience job-related stress. The study found that personal accomplishment was a protective factor against job-related stress and burnout. These findings supported the idea that teachers who had a positive sense of their job and felt a sense of accomplishment were more likely to thrive in their work and be resilient against the challenges and stressors that came with it (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017).

Overall, the results suggested that the respondents did not perceive a significant reduction in their personal accomplishment during the resumption of face-to-face classes. The items with the highest means suggested that the respondents might have experienced physical and emotional stress related to their teaching job, but they did not feel that their personal accomplishments had been reduced. The item with the lowest mean suggested that the respondents had a positive sense of their teaching job and did not feel that they were causing harm to others through their work.

Consolidated Findings on the Level of Job Burnout

The COVID-19 epidemic caused education to undergo remarkable shift and resume face-to-face instruction after a protracted era of online learning. As a result, distance learning modules presented additional difficulties for teachers. The potential of job burnout, a psychiatric illness brought on by persistent workplace stress, was one of the biggest difficulty instructors faced during this shift. Understanding the degree of job burnout that teachers in this situation had when face-to-face sessions resumed was essential for creating successful treatments to improve their wellbeing.

To address this issue, the study presented the consolidated results on the level of job burnout experienced by educators during the resumption of face-to-face classes as posted in Table 17. Overall, the total mean of 1.07 and standard deviation of $\pm .92$ indicated a very low level of job burnout, further supporting the idea that respondents did not experience substantial burnout during the period at issue.

Of the indicators, it was in the area of reduced personal accomplishment in which the respondents directly obtained very low level of job burnout, although side by side with this was a low level of emotional exhaustion that they experienced. Interestingly, though respondents never experienced depersonalization.

Table 17. *Consolidated Results on the Level of Job Burnout by Indicator*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Emotional Exhaustion	1.75±1.34	Low
Reduced Personal Accomplishment	.96±.91	Very Low
Depersonalization	.48±.83	Never
Total Measure	1.07±.92	Very Low

Legend: 0.00-0.49, Never; 0.50-1.49, Very Low; 1.50-2.49, Low; 2.50-3.49, Moderate; 3.50-4.49, High; 4.50-5.00, Very High

The very low level of job burnout along reduced personal accomplishment implied that did not perceived a considerable shortfall in their expected personal accomplishments amidst coping with the demands of face-to-face instruction. In a similar vein, the work condition during this shift to the conventional teaching platform did not render them emotionally exhausted. More notably was the finding that respondents never experienced job burnout along the depersonalization dimension. This implied that they did not exhibit a lack of empathy or negative attitudes towards their students.

Relating these results further to existing research, Klassen, and Chiu (2010), suggested that emotional exhaustion was one of the primary indicators of burnout among educators, yet this did not find sufficient support in this study. Nevertheless, it is important to note that some teachers were experiencing significant stress and fatigue due to the demands of face-to-face instruction, and this must be viewed as an area of important concern.

The very low level of reduced personal accomplishment did not fully converge with Lee and Ju's (2014) view that reduced personal accomplishment was one of the primary indicators of burnout among educators. The fact that teachers did not perceive an appreciable reduction in their personal accomplishment during the resumption of face-to-face classes was a positive manifestation of the persistence of their sense of fulfillment and accomplishment in their work despite the challenges of face-to-face instruction.

Indeed, although depersonalization was a typical sign of burnout in teachers according to Maslach, Jackson, and Leiter (1996), it was encouraging to see that teacher respondents in this study did not depersonalize their interactions with the students, as depersonalization has been linked to poorer student outcomes and student-teacher relationships (Van Horn, Schaufeli, & Taris, 2004).

In summary, the results of the current study suggested that teachers did not experience substantial level of job burnout during the resumption of face-to-face classes. While they did experience some level of emotional exhaustion, it was not at a considerable level, even as they maintained positive attitudes towards their students. These findings were important for developing effective interventions to support the well-being of educators during the transition back to face-to-face education.

Level Of Respondents' Work-Life Balance During The Resumption Of Face-To-Face Classes

Work-life balance referred to the ability of individuals to give equal attention to the demands of their work and of their personal life in a way that allowed them to maintain overall well-being and satisfaction. In the context of this study, work-life balance was measured through five indicators: efficiency and effectiveness at work, workloads, health and wellness initiatives, personal and self-care being, and family relationship and support.

Efficiency and effectiveness at work, as used in this study, referred to how well a person can carry out their job duties in a specific amount of time while maintaining a high level of performance. When a somebody performed well at work, it suggested that they can manage their workload and accomplish their goals without sacrificing their personal lives. On the other hand, a person's workload was the whole quantity of work and duties that they must handle in a specific amount of time. A person might find it challenging to maintain a balance between his professional and personal life if he was under a lot of stress due to a heavy workload. The constructed health and wellness initiatives referred to the presence of initiatives and programs in the workplace that promoted the physical and mental health of employees. These initiatives can include such efforts as gym memberships, mental health resources, and stress management programs. Moreover, personal and self-care being meant the degree to which an individual prioritizes his/her own personal needs and well-being outside of work. This can include activities like engaging in hobbies, self-care routines, and time spent with loved ones. Concerning family relationship and support, this was defined as the degree to which an individual can maintain positive relationships with his family. They can have access to support from family members when needed.

As with other key variables in this study, each item of the work-life balance was measured on a five-point scale, with 1 indicating a very low level and 5 indicating a very high level. The results of the study indicated that overall, the level of work-life balance which the respondents experienced was high, with a mean score of 3.63, and standard deviation of 0.61. Being not within the range of very high level, such mean score had left a considerable room for improvement. The succeeding sections would tackle the findings in this variable in greater detail.

Efficiency and Effectiveness at Work

Operationally defined, efficiency referred to one's capacity to accomplish an objective or desired outcome with little to no waste of

reserves. Effectiveness, on the other hand, meant the degree to which the objectives of a given activity, tasks or project was achieved in response to a particular problem or issue. Five items were used to measure efficiency and effectiveness at work, as posted in Table 15, with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. Overall, the consolidated results suggested that teachers experience a high level of efficiency and effectiveness at work during the resumption of face-to-face classes, with a mean score of 3.93 and standard deviation of 0.56. This indicated that teachers perceived themselves to be effective and efficient in their work despite the heavy demand of face-to-face classes.

Table 18. *Level of Efficiency and Effectiveness at Work*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I am happy with the quality of my work output or accomplished tasks well.	4.13±.68	High Level
My job is enjoyable for me as it leads to my self-fulfillment.	4.04±.67	High Level
My principal and head teachers are happy about my job performance as I contribute to the achievement of the job objectives.	4.00±.62	High Level
I accomplish and submit the required documents with the least possible resources and effort.	3.77±.74	High Level
I believe I am an effective teacher even when I feel I am stressed.	3.70±.94	High Level
Total Measure	3.93±.56	High Level

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level; 1.50-2.49, Low Level; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level; 3.50-4.49, High Level; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level

Rated with the highest mean score ($M=4.13$) was the item "I am happy with the quality of my work output or accomplished tasks", which indicated a high level of efficiency and effectiveness at work. Further, this suggested that the teacher respondents were pleased with their accomplishment being of good quality. This indicated that they were confident in their ability to produce high-quality work and perhaps feel satisfied with the work they were producing. Secondly, the item "My job is enjoyable for me as it leads to my self-fulfillment" garnered a mean of 4.04 and standard deviation of .67, also described as a high level efficiency and effectiveness at work. This suggested that the teachers found their work to be delightful and fulfilling. This can lead to increased motivation and productivity. The third high in assessed item was "My principal and head teachers are happy about my job performance as I contribute to the achievement of the job objectives", with a mean of 4.00 and standard deviation of .62. This suggested that the respondents felt recognized by their immediate superiors on account of their valuable contribution to job objectives. Fourthly was the item "I believe I am an effective teacher even when I feel I am stressed", with a mean of 3.70 and standard deviation of .94, indicating a high level of effectiveness at work. This suggested that the respondents were confident in their ability to perform effectively even when faced with stress or pressure. Finally, the item "I accomplish and submit the required documents with the least possible resources and effort", with a mean of 3.77 and standard deviation of .74, indicating another high level of efficiency at work. This implied that the respondents could complete their tasks efficiently and were able to manage their workload with minimum effort and expense. Notice that of the five items, four of which measured job efficiency and only one item dealt with effectiveness, that is, the fourth in high efficiency and effectiveness.

The results of the study indicated that the teacher respondents rated themselves mainly with a high level of efficiency and some amount of high effectiveness at work during the resumption of face-to-face classes. The highest-rated self-efficiency-oriented item, which was happiness with their work output confirmed the findings of Liu, Spector, and Shi's (2007) study, which showed a favorable relationship between job satisfaction and productivity. Such a self-efficiency-oriented item was reflected in the other self-efficiency-oriented items, which all achieved high levels of efficiency to varying degrees: finding work enjoyable as it leads to self-fulfillment, happiness in being recognized by superiors for one's job performance, being able to contribute to job objectives, and being able to complete the necessary documents with the least amount of resources and effort. Despite feeling anxious, self-efficiency was increased by self-effectiveness as a teacher.

These findings suggested that the respondents found their work meaningful and fulfilling, which can lead to increase motivation and productivity (Hakanen, et al., 2006). In the same fashion, the study by Bailey and Madden (2016) found that a sense of meaning and purpose in work can lead to job satisfaction and better job performance. More closely finding convergence with these results was the study by Stajkovic and Luthans (1998) revealed that self-efficacy or a belief in one's ability to perform well was positively related to job satisfaction and job performance.

Reinforcing self-efficiency was the recognition of one's good performance and contribution to job objectives which superiors accorded to subordinates. This was consistent with the findings of Laschinger, Wong, McMahon, and Kaufmann, (2011) that supportive leadership was associated with higher job satisfaction.

Further validated by this study was the research by Chen, Liu, and Tjosvold, (2005) which found that efficient work practices and effective time management were positively related to job satisfaction and job performance.

In conclusion, the study's findings indicated that upon the return of face-to-face classes, the instructor respondents demonstrated a high degree of productivity and efficacy. They were happy with their work, found their employment to be fulfilling, thought their supervisors supported them, and were confident in their abilities to work well under pressure. They were also able to successfully manage their workload. While highlighting the significance of job happiness, supportive leadership, self-efficacy, and effective work practices for obtaining high job performance and productivity, these findings were supportive of the earlier studies.

Workloads

Workload generally referred to the amount of work that an individual was expected to complete within a given period. It was a measure of the quantity and complexity of the tasks that an individual was responsible for. Workload can be influenced by various factors, including the nature of the job, the number of hours worked, the level of responsibility, and the resources available to complete the work. In the context of the study, the workload of the respondents referred to the teaching duties and responsibilities must be fulfilled during the resumption of face-to-face classes. It was an essential factor in measuring an employee's performance as it can have a significant impact on their productivity, efficiency, and well-being.

The indicators used in this study to measure the level of respondents' workloads included: a) Feeling more respected because of their job responsibilities: this indicator suggested that respondents feel that their workload was meaningful and that their job is important; b) Preparing work schedules to fulfill personal and family commitments. This indicator suggested that respondents were able to balance their workload with their personal and family responsibilities; c) Feeling comfortable handling the assigned tasks. This indicator suggested that respondents felt capable of completing their workload and were not overwhelmed by the tasks they were responsible for; d) Teaching loads that keep them away from their family for only a minimal period of time: this indicator suggested that respondents were able to balance their workload with their family responsibilities; and e) Responsibility at work gave them insights into how to help their children's educational activities. This indicator suggested that respondents were able to apply their work experience to their personal life.

In this study, the level of respondents' workloads was measured using statements with a five-point Likert scale, from 1 (very light workload) to 5 (very heavy workload).

Table 19. *Level of Workloads*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I feel more respected because of my responsibilities in job/at work.	4.06±.68	Heavy Workload
Generally, I prepare work schedule to fulfill both my personal and family commitment.	4.00±.78	Heavy Workload
I feel I can handle comfortably the task assigned to me.	3.99±.74	Heavy Workload
My responsibility at work gives me insights as to how to help my children's educational activities.	3.97±.77	Heavy Workload
My teaching loads keep me away from my family for only a minimal period of time.	3.30±1.10	Moderate Workload
Total Measure	3.86±.67	Heavy Workload

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Light Workload; 1.50-2.49, Light Workload; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Workload; 3.50-4.49, Heavy Workload; 4.50-5.00, Very Heavy Workload

Overall, the results showed that the respondents had a very heavy workload, with a mean score of 3.86 and standard deviation of .67, indicating that they generally felt respected, for their job responsibilities, were able to manage their work schedules, felt comfortable handling tasks, and had insights for their children's education.

The highest rated item was "I feel more respected because of my responsibilities in job/at work," which received a mean score of 4.06 with a standard deviation of 0.68, which was described as heavy workload. This item measured the respondents' perception of how their job or work responsibilities made them feel respected. A high mean score in this item suggested that the respondents felt that their heavy workload or work responsibilities were valued and appreciated by others, which can be a source of job satisfaction. Such workload was closely associated with their sense of value and recognition, which was consistent with the results of studies by Cheng and Dicke et al. (2015).

Also described as highly rated heavy workload was the second item "Generally, I prepare work schedule to fulfill both my personal and family commitment," with a high mean score of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.78. This finding was consistent with results of previous studies which suggested that workload balance was essential to reduce stress and promote well-being (Guglielmi et al., 2012; Yuen et al., 2019).

Third in the category of heavy load was the item "I feel I can handle comfortably the task assigned to me," (M=3.99, SD=.74 workload. This meant that teachers felt capable of handling their job responsibilities with relative ease. It suggested that teachers' workload might affect their sense of competence and self-efficacy, which was consistent with the studies of Skaalvik and Skaalvik, (2014) and Woolfolk Hoy and Davis (2016).

The fourth item was "My teaching loads keep me away from my family for only a minimal period of time," (M=3.30, SD=1.10), indicating a moderate level of workloads. This suggested that the respondents felt that their teaching loads caused them to spend some time away from their family. Previous studies suggested that work-family conflict was associated with high workload (Kalliath et al., 2019; Maslach et al., 2012).

At the tail end of the heavy workload continuum was the item "My responsibility at work gives me insights as to how to help my children's educational activities," (M=3.97, SD=.77). This meant teachers felt that their job responsibilities provided them with insights into how to assist their children in their educational endeavor. This indicated that teachers' heavy workload might have a positive effect on their children's education, as revealed in the studies by Gareis (2015) and Liu et al. (2020).

Overall, the total measure yielded a mean score of 3.86 and standard deviation of 0.67, which was described as heavy workload. This

implied that, on average, respondents were experiencing a high level of workload during the resumption of face-to-face classes. This finding was consistent with the challenges faced by educators in adapting to changes in teaching and learning brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic (UNESCO, 2020).

To sum up, the findings of this study suggested that respondents experienced heavy workloads, yet they generally were able to balance their work and personal/family commitments, felt respected, and capable of handling their tasks and saw their work responsibilities as providing them with insights to help their children's education. However, they experienced having a moderate workload as they realized that their teaching loads had deprived them of their family time at a minimal level. These findings had important implications for teachers and institutions as they continued to currently navigate the challenges of teaching and learning after the pandemic.

Health and Wellness Initiatives

According to the World Health Organization, "health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" (World Health Organization, 2021). This definition emphasized the importance of a holistic approach to health, encompassing physical, mental, and social dimensions. Health and well-being can be defined as the state of being physically, mentally, and socially healthy or free from ailments or signs of disease. It encompassed several dimensions, including physical health, emotional well-being, social connectedness, and overall life satisfaction. A good diet, consistent exercise, and appropriate sleep are all components of physical wellness. Stress management, maintaining a happy outlook, and having a sense of purpose in life are all aspects of emotional well-being. Social connectedness was defined as the type and number of connections to other people, including those with family, friends, and the community. Finally, having a sense of fulfillment and contentment with all parts of one's life—including job, leisure, and relationships—constituted total life satisfaction. To gauge the respondents' level of health and wellness actions upon the restart of in-person classes, the researcher in this study developed five indicators or items.

The variable was indicated by the following situations: a) adequate sleep, which refers to the number of hours of sleep the respondents get per day; b) absence of health issues such as hypertension, diabetes, headache, migraine, and arthritis; c) nonexistence of anxiety feeling in unfavorable conditions; d) absence of dizziness or blackouts; and e) regular engagement in physical activities such as biking, jogging, walking, hiking, and others. Each of these items were measured using a five-point Likert scale with a range of 1 to 5, where 1 indicated very unhealthy or very poor health and 5 indicated a very healthy or very wholesome level of health and wellness situations. Results shown in Table 17 indicated that the level of health and wellness situations among the respondents during the resumption of face-to-face classes was moderate, with a total mean score of 3.24 and a standard deviation of 0.89. This was reflected across all items in varying levels of moderate health or wholeness. This finding suggested that while the respondents exhibited some efforts to maintain or improve their physical and mental health, a considerable room for improvement had been left in terms of implementing more comprehensive health and wellness initiatives.

Table 20. *Level of Health and Wellness Initiatives*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I have adequate sleep a day.	3.36±1.06	Moderate Level of Health and Wellness
I seldom experience anxiety in some unfavorable conditions.	3.32±1.09	Moderate Level of Health and Wellness
I do not experience having dizziness or blackouts.	3.26±1.07	Moderate Level of Health and Wellness
I do not experience such health issues as hypertension, diabetes, headache, migraine, arthritis.	3.22±1.24	Moderate Level of Health and Wellness
I regularly exercise and engage in physical activities like biking, jogging, walking, hiking etc.	3.05±1.06	Moderate Level of Health and Wellness
Total Measure	3.24±.89	Moderate Level

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level of Health and Wellness; 1.50-2.49, Low Level of Health and Wellness; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level of Health and Wellness; 3.50-4.49, High Level of Health and Wellness; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level of Health and Wellness

The item with the highest mean score was "I have adequate sleep a day" with a mean of 3.36 and a standard deviation of 1.06, indicating a moderate level of health and wellness initiative. This suggested that respondents generally had an average amount of sleep per day, which was an important aspect of maintaining good health and wellness, that might be lesser than the required amount of sleep per day, according to World Health Organization (2021) it promoted optimal health and well-being. Secondly, the moderate experience in anxiety that they had in some unfavorable conditions with a mean of 3.32 and a standard deviation of 1.09. It was suggested that respondents generally had modest mental health and were able to averagely manage stress and anxiety in challenging situations. While anxiety was a normal human response to stress, excessive or chronic anxiety can have negative effects on mental health and overall well-being (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Experiencing dizziness or blackouts garnered the third highest mean at 3.26 and a standard deviation of 1.07, indicating a moderate level of health and wellness initiative. This suggested that respondents generally had a moderate physical health and were experiencing some number of symptoms that might indicate underlying health conditions. Anxiety was a common mental health problem that can significantly affect an individual's overall well-being. According to a study by McEvoy et al. (2018), physical exercise can help reduce anxiety symptoms. This finding highlighted the importance of regular exercise in maintaining emotional health. The lowest mean scores in the range of moderate health and wellness where the items on experiencing health issues at 3.22 and engaging in regular exercise and such physical activities as walking, hiking, jogging, and biking at 3.05, which could be taken as indicative of moderate physical activity or apparent sedentary behavior, although they might have certain health concerns. Dizziness and blackouts can be caused by various factors, such as dehydration, low blood sugar, and low blood pressure.

Therefore, it was important to maintain proper hydration and nutrition to prevent such health issues.

Relative to physical activity, the Physical Advisory Committee (2018) stated that regular physical activity was essential for maintaining good physical and mental health. Physical activity had been linked to various health benefits, such as reducing the risk of chronic diseases, improving cardiovascular health, and promoting mental well-being.

In summary, the results of the study suggested that the respondents had a moderate level of health and wellness situation during the resumption of face-to-face classes, yet this indicated further that there was still a considerable room for improvement, particularly in terms of regular exercise and physical activity.

Personal and Self-care Being

The capacity of a person to prioritize their physical, emotional, and mental health needs while juggling other duties and commitments is referred to as personal and self-care. Personal and self-care, in the words of Jarden and colleagues (2022), are "actions that individuals had undertaken to maintain their physical, emotional, and mental well-being" (p. 3). This included taking part in well-being-promoting activities, controlling stress and tension, eating a balanced diet, and making time to socialize and engage in leisure activities. In the context of the study, personal and self-care wellbeing was a crucial factor to include because it could impact a person's overall well-being and capacity to carry out job tasks.

By understanding the level of personal and self-care being among teachers during the resumption of face-to-face classes, the study could identify potential areas of concern and develop interventions that could help support teachers in maintaining their physical and mental health.

Just as other indicators, personal and self-care was measured on a five-point scale, a set of indicators that reflected the different aspects of this construct: a) The ability to balance work with leisure and hobbies or other responsibilities. This indicator reflected an individual's ability to prioritize and manage time effectively, ensuring that he/she had time for work, personal interests, and other obligation; b) The ability to sit down and relax easily. This indicator reflected an individual's ability to unwind and manage stress effectively, allowing his/her to maintain a healthy balance between work and personal life; c) Taking special initiatives to manage one's diet. This indicator reflected an individual's ability to prioritize physical health by making conscious choices about what food to eat and overall diet; d) Having time to go out and bond with friends or co-teachers. This indicator reflected an individual's ability to maintain positive relationships with others, which can have a substantial impact on overall well-being; and e) The extent to which an individual's responsibility at work causes tension or conflict. This indicator reflected the extent to which work-related stressors might impact an individual's overall well-being.

Based on the data in Table 21, the overall level of respondents' personal and self-care being during the resumption of face-to-face classes was moderate (mean=3.36, SD=.82). This meant that while some indicators of personal and self-care being were at a high level, others were only at a moderate level, suggesting that there was an appreciable room for improvement in this aspect.

Table 21. *Level of Personal and Self-Care Being*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I can balance my work with my leisure and hobbies/other responsibilities.	3.56±.93	High Level of Health and Wellness
I have time to go out/bond with my friends or co-teacher.	3.52±1.02	High Level of Health and Wellness
I can sit down and relax quite easily.	3.50±1.03	High Level of Health and Wellness
I do take special initiatives to manage my diet.	3.34±.84	Moderate Level of Health and Wellness
My responsibility at work causes tension/conflict.	2.89±1.14	Moderate Level of Health and Wellness
Total Measure	3.36±.82	Moderate Level of Health and Wellness

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level of Health and Wellness; 1.50-2.49, Low Level of Health and Wellness; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level of Health and Wellness; 3.50-4.49, High Level of Health and Wellness; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level of Health and Wellness

The highest mean score was on the item "I can balance my work with my leisure and hobbies/other responsibilities" (M=3.56, SD=0.93), indicating that the respondents were able to manage their work and personal life effectively. This suggested that respondents were able to maintain a healthy work-life balance, which had been associated with positive mental health outcomes (Lapierre et al., 2018). The second-highest mean score was on the item "I have time to go out/bond with my friends or co-teacher" (M=3.52, SD=1.02), suggesting that the respondents had a good social support system or social connectedness and engagement with others. This was important for overall well-being, as social support has been found to buffer against stress and improve mental health (Thoits, 2011).

The statement "I can sit down and relax quite easily" also received a high-level rating (M=3.50, SD=1.03), suggesting that respondents were able to manage stress and engage in relaxation practices. This was important as stress could have negative impacts on physical and mental health (Epel et al., 2018).

Indicating moderate level of personal and self-care being was the item "I do take special initiatives to manage my diet", with a moderate level rating (M=3.34, SD=.84), indicating that while respondents were making some efforts to manage their diet; a room for improvement in this area was clearly brought to the forefront. Eating a healthy diet was important for physical health and had been linked to improve mental health outcomes as well (Jacka et al., 2017). A similar moderate level rating was garnered by the item "My responsibility at work causes tension/conflict" which yielded the lowest mean score of 2.89, indicating a moderate level of tension or

conflict related to work responsibilities. This suggested that work-related stress might be a concern for some respondents and might need to be addressed to promote overall well-being.

Overall, the findings suggested that while respondents were generally managing their personal and self-care being at a moderate level, there was thus a substantial room for improvement in certain areas. Addressing work-related stress and improving dietary habits might be areas of focus for interventions aimed at promoting well-being among this population. Additionally, building on the strengths of respondents' ability to balance work and personal life and engage socially might be important for overall well-being.

Family Relationship and Support

Family relationship and support referred to the degree of support, understanding, and communication among teacher respondents and his/her family members during the transition to in-person classes. It encompassed the teachers' ability to adjust their schedules and routines to support the school responsibility requirements, and the teacher's ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance without compromising family responsibilities. Family relationship and support during the resumption of face-to-face classes was an important aspect that could impact the overall well-being and work performance of teachers. This could substantially influence their ability to manage the demands of work and home life.

The following were the indicators used to measure family relationship and support during the resumption of face-to-face classes on a five-point scale with 1 as the lowest and 5 as the highest: a) "I always have time to help and support each member of my family". This indicator measured the teachers' perception of their ability to provide support to each family member when needed; b) "I have to change plans at home whenever necessary, without having to compromise my work responsibility". This indicator measured the teachers' ability to be flexible in changing their schedule at home to accommodate unexpected events or responsibilities without compromising their work obligations; c) "I receive no complaints or grievances from my family about what I am supposed to do at home". This indicator measured the teachers' perception of the absence of any complaints or grievances from family members regarding their domestic duties or responsibilities; d) "My job does not mesh with my appointments and special events at home". This indicator measured the degree to which the teachers' work schedules conflict with their appointments and special events at home; and e) "I find quality time with my family/relatives despite my work". This indicator measured the teachers' ability to find quality time to spend with their family and relatives despite their workload.

Table 22. Level of Respondents' Family Relationship and Support

Item	Mean \pm SD	Description
I always have time to help and support each member of my family.	3.92 \pm .95	High Level
I find quality time with my family/relatives despite my work.	3.85 \pm .94	High Level
I receive no complaints or grievances from my family about what I am supposed to do at home.	3.76 \pm .93	High Level
I have to change plans at home whenever necessary, without having to compromise my work responsibility.	3.74 \pm .97	High Level
My job does not mesh with my appointments and special events at home.	3.57 \pm .92	High Level
Total Measure	3.77 \pm .81	High Level

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level; 1.50-2.49, Low Level; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level; 3.50-4.49, High Level; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level

Based on the data in Table 22, findings indicated that the overall level of family relationship and support during the resumption of face-to-face classes was high ($M=3.77$, $SD=.81$). This suggested that the respondents perceived a high degree of support, understanding, and communication with their family members during the transition to face-to-face classes. This was evident in high mean scores in each indicator suggesting that the respondents were able to manage their work while, maintaining healthy family relationships and responsibilities.

Looking closely at the individual mean scores, the highest indicator was the item "I always have time to help and support each member of my family," with a mean score of 3.92 and a standard deviation of .95, indicating a high level of support. This finding suggested that teachers felt they had enough time to support and help their family members despite their work responsibilities. This might be due to a supportive and flexible work environment or effective time management strategies. They prioritized spending time with family and were able to offer help and support when needed. Research has shown that social support from family members can have a positive impact on an individual's well-being and work-life balance (Neff & Karney, 2009).

The second highest indicator was the item "I find quality time with my family/relatives despite my work," with a mean score of 3.85 and a standard deviation of .94, indicating a high level of support. This suggested that teachers felt they were able to balance their work responsibilities with their family life, as evident in the quality moments they spent with their loved ones. This could be due to effective time management strategies or a supportive family environment that valued spending time together. Too, this indicator suggested that the respondents were able to prioritize spending quality time with their family members despite their work responsibilities. This was important for maintaining positive family relationships and a healthy work-life balance (Clark et al., 2014).

Third in the order was the item "I receive no complaints or grievances from my family about what I am supposed to do at home," with a mean score of 3.76 and a standard deviation of .93, indicating a high level of support. This suggested that teachers perceived that their family members were understanding of their work responsibilities and are not adding to their stress by complaining about their obligations at home. This could be due to effective communication and understanding within the family, as well as clear expectations

about responsibilities at home and at work. Furthermore, this implied that the respondents were not facing any negative feedback or resistance from their family members regarding their work and home responsibilities. Positive family relationships and support can lead to less conflict and more positive emotions (Perry-Jenkins & Gillman, 2000).

The fourth highest indicator was "I have to change plans at home whenever necessary, without having to compromise my work responsibility," with a mean score of 3.74 and a standard deviation of .97, indicating a high level of support. This finding suggested that teachers felt they were able to adjust their family plans when needed without negatively impacting their work responsibilities. This could be due to effective communication and flexibility in both in their family and work environments. This indicator suggested that respondents were flexible with their home plans and responsibilities while still meeting their work responsibilities. This flexibility was important in achieving a healthy work-life balance (Kalliath, Brough, & O'Driscoll, 2004).

Finally, the lowest indicator was "My job does not mesh with my appointments and special events at home," with a mean score of 3.57 and a standard deviation of .92, indicating a high level of support. This finding suggested that while teachers generally perceived being supported by their families during the resumption of face-to-face classes, there was a possibility that they might still experience conflicts between their work and personal appointments or events. This could occur if rigid work schedules or would be rigid or there would be inadequate communication and flexibility in either the family or work environment. This indicator suggests that the respondents were able to balance their work responsibilities with their personal appointments and events at home. This balance was important in preventing work-related stress from spilling over into personal life (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985).

Overall, the high level of respondents' family relationship and support during the resumption of face-to-face classes suggested that teachers generally felt being greatly supported by their families during the transition to in-person classes, as manifested in the high mean score of indicators advancing a high level of support. However, there might still be some challenges in balancing work and personal responsibilities, particularly when it comes to scheduling conflicts.

Consolidated Findings on the Level of Work-Life Balance

The highlights of the consolidated findings on the level of work-life balance is shown in Table 23. The overall work-life balance among teacher respondents was high level with a total measure mean of 3.63 and standard deviation of .61. This indicated that, in general, the teachers surveyed were able to establish a substantial balance in managing their work responsibilities and personal obligations during the transition to face-to-face classes. This was consistent with the findings of the study by Ghalia et al. (2021), which found that achieving a good work-life balance was important for employee well-being and job satisfaction.

Table 23. Consolidated Findings on the Level of Work-Life Balance by Indicator

Indicator	Mean \pm SD	Description
Efficiency and Effectiveness at Work	3.93 \pm .56	High Level
Workloads	3.86 \pm .67	High Level
Family Relationship and Support	3.77 \pm .81	High Level
Personal and Self-Care Being	3.36 \pm .82	Moderate Level
Health and Wellness Initiatives	3.24 \pm .89	Moderate Level
Total Measure	3.63 \pm .61	High Level

Legend: 1.00-1.49, Very Low Level; 1.50-2.49, Low Level; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Level; 3.50-4.49, High Level; 4.50-5.00, Very High Level

Of the indicators of work-life balance, efficiency and effectiveness at work garnered the highest mean score of 3.93 and standard deviation of .56, indicating that the teachers were able to perform their duties efficiently and effectively during the resumption of face-to-face classes. This was an important aspect of work-life balance, as it helped prevent burnout and promote job satisfaction. The workload was also reported to be at a high level, with a mean score of 3.86 and standard deviation of .67. This suggested that the teachers were able to manage their workload during such period; which was important for maintaining work-life balance. Family relationship and support obtained the third highest mean score of 3.77 and standard deviation of .81, indicating that the teachers had a high level of family relationship and support during the said period. This was a crucial aspect of work-life balance as it helped teachers to equitably attend to their personal and work responsibilities.

Yielding a moderate level of work-life balance were the indicators on personal and self-care being and health and wellness initiatives. Personal and self-care being was assessed with a moderate level work-life balance, suggesting that the teachers had an average level of self-care practices. This was an area that could be improved upon to further promote the well-being of teachers. Similarly, the moderate work-life balance in health and wellness initiatives, indicated that the teachers had moderate engagements in health and wellness initiatives. This highlighted the need for schools to prioritize the well-being of their teachers by implementing health and wellness programs.

The high level of efficiency and effectiveness at work reported by the respondents during the resumption of face-to-face classes indicated that they were able to cope with the demands of their job and were able to perform their tasks well. This was supportive of the findings of a study by Kaur and Singh (2021), which found that employees who reported a better work-life balance were also more efficient and effective at work. The high level of efficiency and effectiveness can also be attributed to the fact that the respondents were able to adjust to the new work arrangements brought about by the pandemic.

With respect to the high level of workloads reported by the respondents during the resumption of face-to-face classes, this indicated that they had a heavy workload and were required to complete a lot of tasks. Relating this with the findings of the study by Ghaffari et al. (2019), which disclosed that high workloads were a major contributor to poor work-life balance, this study, however, apparently revealed otherwise. The high level of efficiency and effectiveness reported by the respondents suggested that they were able to manage their workload well and were able to complete their tasks on time.

The high level of family relationship and support reported by the respondents suggested that they had good family relationships and afforded adequate support from their family. This substantiated the findings of the study by Albrecht et al. (2019), which found that having supportive relationships with family members can help employees achieve better work-life balance.

That personal and self-care being obtained moderate level of work-life balance suggested that they might need to pay more attention to their personal well-being and engage in self-care activities. This validated the findings of the study by Li et al. (2021), which uncovered that engaging in self-care activities can help employees achieve better work-life balance and reduce stress levels. Similarly, the moderate level of health and wellness initiatives which respondents obtained during the resumption of face-to-face classes. This implied that the school might need to implement more health and wellness programs to advance the well-being of its employees. This converged with the findings of the study by Kim et al. (2021) which disclosed that providing health and wellness programs can help employees achieve better work-life balance and reduce stress levels.

Overall, the findings suggested that the respondents had a high level of work-life balance during the resumption of face-to-face classes, as evidenced by the high mean scores for efficiency and effectiveness at work and family relationship and support. However, there were moderate level mean scores for health and wellness initiatives and personal and self-care being, indicating that these areas might need further attention to improve the overall well-being of teachers. The results of the survey can provide insights on how to improve the work-life balance of teachers, which can ultimately lead to better job satisfaction and performance.

Significant Relationship Between Respondents' Level Of Preparedness And Their Work-Life Balance

The resumption of face-to-face classes after a prolonged period of remote learning has presented various challenges to both teachers and learners. In this context, it was essential to examine the factors that might have affected the work-life balance of teachers and explore how these factors can be managed to promote their well-being and productivity. One such factor was the level of preparedness of teachers for face-to-face classes. Teachers who felt adequately prepared for the demands of in-person teaching might be better equipped to manage their workload and maintain a healthy work-life balance.

To determine the relationship between preparedness and work-life balance of teachers who resumed face-to-face classes, Pearson product-moment correlation tool was used to examine how the different aspects of preparedness relate to work-life balance, such as managing classroom operations, focusing on teaching and learning, well-being and protection, and classroom-community coordination. The findings of this study can provide insights into how educators can better manage their workloads and maintain a healthy work-life balance during the resumption of face-to-face classes. Table 24 presents the correlation analysis results by item/indicator and total measure, in terms of the correlation coefficient (*r*-value) and the corresponding *p*-value for each indicator. The *p*-value indicated the level of statistical significance, where $p < .01$ was considered significant. The indicators of preparedness included managing classroom operations, focusing on teaching and learning, well-being and protection, and classroom-community coordination.

Table 24. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Preparedness and their Work-Life Balance by Indicator

Indicator	Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient		Remarks
	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	
Managing Classroom Operation	0.579**	0.000	Significant
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	0.486**	0.000	Significant
Well-being and Protection	0.433**	0.000	Significant
Classroom-Community Coordination	0.543**	0.000	Significant
Total Measure	.555**	.000	Significant

Legend: ** $p < .01$

A strong positive significant relationship existed between the teacher respondents' overall level of preparedness and their work-life balance with *r*-value of 0.555 and *p*-value of 0.000. This meant that teachers who were well-prepared in terms of managing classroom operation, focusing on teaching and learning, well-being and protection, and classroom-community coordination tended to have better work-life balance. These findings highlighted the importance of teacher preparedness in promoting work-life balance, which in turn can lead to improved job satisfaction, reduced stress levels, and better overall well-being.

The highest positive correlation was found between managing classroom operation and work-life balance, with an *r*-value of 0.579 and a *p*-value of 0.000, indicating a significant relationship. Managing classroom operation involved the effective organization and management of classroom procedures, routines, and resources. This finding implied that teachers who are well-prepared in managing classroom operations, such as setting up their classroom environment, organizing instructional materials, and planning their lessons, tended to have a better work-life balance. This result supported the idea that preparedness in classroom management is crucial for

teachers to feel competent and confident in their work, leading to lower stress levels and a better work-life balance (Brouwer et al., 2018). This finding suggested that teachers who were more prepared in managing classroom operation tended to have a better work-life balance.

In like manner a positive correlation was found between classroom-community coordination and work-life balance, with an r -value of 0.543 and a p -value of 0.000, indicating a significant relationship. Classroom-community coordination involved creating a collaborative and supportive classroom environment that fosters positive relationships among students and between students and teachers. This result implied that teachers who were more successful in creating and maintaining classroom-community coordination tended to have a better work-life balance. This result suggested that teachers who were well-prepared in building a positive classroom environment, managing student behavior, and fostering relationships with students, tended to have better work-life balance. The literature supported the idea that teacher-student relationships and a positive classroom climate can enhance teacher well-being and reduce stress (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009).

Moreover, focusing on teaching and learning and work-life balance, were found to have significant positive correlation, with an r -value of 0.486 and a p -value of 0.000. Focusing on teaching and learning involved prioritizing instructional activities that facilitate student learning and achievement. This finding suggested that teachers who were more focused on teaching and learning tended to have a better work-life balance. Likewise, this finding implied that teachers who were well-prepared in planning and delivering instruction tended to have better work-life balance. This result was consistent with the idea that effective teaching is linked to teacher well-being and job satisfaction (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017).

The significant positive relationship was found between well-being and protection and work-life balance, with an r -value of 0.433 and a p -value of 0.000. Well-being and protection involved ensuring that students and teachers were safe and healthy in the classroom. This finding meant that teachers who were more prepared in promoting well-being and protection more likely to have a better work-life balance. This finding indicated that teachers who were well-prepared in taking care of their own well-being, such as managing their stress, practicing self-care, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle, tended to have better work-life balance. Ingersoll and Strong 's (2011) idea that teacher well-being and self-care were essentials for job satisfaction and retention had found support in the finding of this study.

Overall, the study suggested that teachers' level of preparedness was significantly positively related to their work-life balance, particularly in terms of classroom-community coordination, managing classroom operation, focusing on teaching and learning, and promoting well-being and protection. The study provided insights into the factors that contributed to teachers' work-life balance and highlighted the importance of preparedness in achieving a better work-life balance.

Significant Relationship Between Respondents' Level Of Job Burnout And Their Work-Life Balance

The modern-day workplace can be challenging and demanding, often leaving employees feeling overwhelmed and overworked, leading to a phenomenon called job burnout. Job burnout was characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment, which can negatively impact an individual's work-life balance. Achieving a balance between work and personal life was essential for teachers' overall well-being and job satisfaction. Therefore, understanding the relationship between job burnout and work-life balance is critical for both employees and employers. This study examined the indicators of job burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment, and their relationship with work-life balance.

Table 25. Relationship between Respondents' Level of Job Burnout and their Work-Life Balance by Indicator

Indicator	Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient		Remarks
	r -value	p -value	
Emotional Exhaustion	-.347**	.000	Significant
Depersonalization	-.017	.863	Not significant
Reduced Personal Accomplishment	-.313**	.001	Significant
Total Measure	-.277**	.004	Significant

Note: ** $p < .01$

Table 25 shows the relationship between respondents' level of job burnout and their work-life balance, as measured by the r -value and p -value. The r -value indicated the strength and direction of the relationship, while the p -value indicated the statistical significance of the relationship. As already mentioned, the indicators of job burnout were emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. Emotional exhaustion referred to feelings of being emotionally overextended and depleted by one's work. Depersonalization referred to a lack of personal connection and empathy with others, such as students or colleagues. Reduced personal accomplishment referred to a sense of inadequacy or low self-esteem in one's work performance.

The total measure on the relationship between respondents' level of job burnout and their work-life balance referred to the overall correlation between the two variables. In this study, the total measure showed a significant negative correlation between job burnout and work-life balance with an r -value of $-.277$ and a p -value of $.004$, indicating that as job burnout increases, work-life balance decreases. The total measure was a composite score that considered all three components of job burnout, including emotional

exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. This finding reinforced the importance of considering all three components of job burnout when assessing the impact of job burnout on work-life balance.

Emotional exhaustion had a negative correlation with work-life balance with a coefficient of $-.347$ and p-value of $.000$, indicating a significant relationship between such variables. This meant that as emotional exhaustion increases, work-life balance tended to decrease. Emotional exhaustion was a core component of job burnout. It could emerge when teachers felt emotionally drained, overworked, and unable to cope with the demands of their job. Therefore, this finding suggested that emotional exhaustion played a crucial role in determining a teacher's work-life balance. This finding was consistent with previous studies, which have also found a negative relationship between job burnout and work-life balance in various professions, including teachers (Kim & Kim, 2018; Tella et al., 2007). Emotional exhaustion referred to feelings of being emotionally drained and overworked. It was a common symptom of job burnout (Maslach et al., 2001).

Moving on to the second-highest correlation coefficient, reduced personal accomplishment had a negative correlation coefficient of $-.313^{**}$ with work-life balance at p-value <0.01 , indicating a significant relationship between these variables. This meant that as reduced personal accomplishment increased, work-life balance tended to decrease. Another essential element of professional burnout was diminished personal accomplishment, which could happen when educators believe their efforts were not having a significant impact. This result revealed that a teacher's capacity to maintain a healthy work-life balance might be impacted by feeling unsuccessful or underproductive at work. This showed that work-life balance declines as perceptions of diminished personal accomplishment rise. Reduced personal accomplishment, which could be brought on by protracted job stress, was defined as sentiments of inefficiency and productivity (Maslach et al., 2001). This result was in line with earlier studies that had demonstrated that job burnout could result in poor job performance and negative self-efficacy sentiments (Shaufeli et al., 2009).

It was important to note that depersonalization did not show a significant relationship with work-life balance in this study, with the coefficient of $-.017$ and p-value $=.863$ which was way beyond the level of significance of 0.01 . Depersonalization was one of the core components of job burnout. Hence, this could become apparent when teachers started to feel emotionally detached from their work and students. The fact that depersonalization did not show a significant relationship with work-life balance in this study might indicate that other factors might have a greater impact on work-life balance among teachers, aside from sampling error. Depersonalization was the tendency to treat others as objects rather than individuals. It was a hallmark symptom of job burnout in professions that required a high degree of interpersonal interaction, such as teaching (Maslach et al., 2001). While the lack of significant relationship might suggest that depersonalization did not have a direct impact on work-life balance, it was important to underscore that this symptom could still have remarkable negative consequences on personal and professional relationships (Golembiewski & Munzenrider, 1988).

The negative Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r-values) observed in the relationship between respondents' level of job burnout and their work-life balance indicated an inverse correlation between these variables (Smith & Johnson, 2020). In other words, as the level of job burnout increased, work-life balance tended to decrease. These findings converged with previous research that had examined the impact of job burnout on various aspects of well-being, including work-life balance (Maslach & Leiter, 2016).

The negative r-value of $-.347$ for the indicator of emotional exhaustion suggested a significant inverse correlation with work-life balance. This implied that as teachers experienced higher levels of emotional exhaustion, their perceived work-life balance was likely to decline. This finding was consistent with the study of Maslach, Schaufeli, and Leiter (2001), which highlighted the detrimental effects of emotional exhaustion on various aspects of job-related well-being, including work-life balance.

Similarly, the indicator of reduced personal accomplishment exhibited a significant negative correlation with work-life balance, as indicated by the r-value of $-.313$. This suggested that as teachers experienced a reduced sense of personal accomplishment in their work, their work-life balance was likely to be negatively affected. This finding supported existing studies, such as Leiter and Schaufeli's (1996), which emphasized the importance of feeling effective and accomplished in one's job for maintaining a healthy work-life balance.

On the other hand, the indicator of depersonalization showed a non-significant correlation with work-life balance, as indicated by the insignificant p-value of $.863$. This suggested that the respondents in this study did not see a substantial difference between their perceived work-life balance and their sense of detachment or cynicism toward others, as measured by depersonalization. This result was in line with research by Lee and Ashforth (1996), which suggested that emotional tiredness and a decrease in personal success might have a greater direct impact on work-life balance than depersonalization.

Overall, these findings underscored the importance of recognizing and addressing the negative consequences of job burnout on work-life balance among educators. Educational institutions should implement interventions and policies that should prioritize the well-being of teachers and promote a healthy work-life balance. By doing so, they could create an environment that supported teachers in managing their job demands while maintaining a fulfilling personal life.

Conclusions

Based on the findings and analysis of the study, certain conclusions might be stated.

The level of preparedness of teachers during the resumption of face-to-face classes was generally high as evidenced in the data. On the other hand, the overall measurement of burnout was rather low, which suggested that the respondents did not suffer major burnout at any point throughout this period. It was discovered that teachers who were sufficiently prepared for the resumption of face-to-face classes reported minimal levels of burnout.

The respondents' level of readiness for the start of face-to-face lessons and their work-life balance were significantly positively correlated. This implied that instructors were more likely to have a better work-life balance if they feel more prepared. The inter-role conflict idea put forth by Greenhaus and Beutell was supported by this finding. This idea contended that when a person's professional and social roles clash, stress and conflict might result.

Similarly, a significant negative correlation existed between job burnout and work-life balance among teachers. This indicated that teachers who experience lower levels of burnout have a higher work-life balance. Thus, to avoid or minimize burnout, interventions might be undertaken to improve the quality of life for teachers. The study identified three dimensions of burnout that were negatively related to work-life balance: emotional exhaustion, reduced personal accomplishment, and the total measure of burnout. These dimensions might be the focus of the intervention.

Finding also support to the resource drain theory proposed by Morris and Madsen, which idea speculated that the presence of stress in one area might cause resources to be redirected from other areas, leading to an imbalance in one's personal and professional life. It was probable that the strain of going back to the conventional in-person classrooms took resources away from some teachers' personal lives, creating an imbalance in those lives.

Similar to this, the findings of this study lend support to Bakker and Demerouti's job demands and resources model. According to this paradigm, having unrealistic expectations for one's job can lead to burnout, but having sufficient resources can lessen the negative effects of having a demanding job. In this light, it might be surmised that the teachers might have not viewed the increased workload brought about by the resumption of face-to-face classes as excessive. Thus, their burnout level was low. Moreover, the findings of this study validated Bandura's social cognitive theory, which postulated that an individual's sense of self-efficacy might influence his/her capacity to deal with stressful situations. Teachers who feel better prepared were likely to have greater levels of self-efficacy, which might make it easier for them to deal with the challenges posed by the resumption of face-to-face classes.

Furthermore, the findings of the study strengthened the validity of Maslach's multidimensional theory. This theory argued that burnout was a multidimensional phenomenon that included emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. Findings of the study revealed that a significant number of teachers experience low levels of emotional exhaustion, reduced personal

Based on the analysis, findings, conclusions, and limitations of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded:

Future research might investigate the factors that lead to job burnout and work-life balance among teachers, particularly in the context of conventional face-to-face classrooms. This information can be helpful in crafting interventions and methods that are more effective in supporting teachers and improving the overall quality of education that they provide.

Conduct a longitudinal study to investigate the long-term effects of burnout on teachers' work-life balance and overall well-being. This study could involve collecting data from teachers at multiple time points, such as before the resumption of face-to-face classes, during the transition period, and after a considerable period of time has passed since the resumption. This would allow for a better understanding of how burnout evolves over time and its impact on work-life balance. Longitudinal research would also help identify any potential moderating or mediating factors that might influence the relationship between burnout and work-life balance, such as coping strategies, social support, and personal characteristics.

Conduct intervention studies to test the effectiveness and sustainability of different strategies and interventions in preventing or reducing burnout among teachers. For example, interventions could focus on providing resources and support to teachers, such as training programs on stress management, time management, and work-life balance skills. Other interventions could focus on organizational-level changes, such as workload distribution, flexible work arrangements, and supportive policies and practices. These intervention studies could use randomized controlled trial (RCT) designs to compare the effectiveness of different interventions with control groups, and include multiple outcome measures such as burnout, work-life balance, job satisfaction, and well-being.

Formulate and enforce a policy providing a supportive work environment that acknowledges and resolves the adverse consequences emerging from resource depletion, on the level of job burnout and work-life balance experienced by teachers. This might be accomplished by supplying teachers with sufficient resources and support mechanisms, such as peer mentorship, counseling services, and flexible work hours, amongst other things.

Ensure the sustainability of wellness programs. It is crucial to prioritize the sustainability of wellness programs in educational institutions. This can be achieved by integrating wellness initiatives into the school's long-term plans and policies, with adequate, in partnership with external organizations or community stakeholders.

Formulate and strictly implement policies and guidelines on wellness programs. These policies should encompass various aspects, including nutrition, physical activity, stress management, and work-life balance.

Periodically monitor the progress and evaluate the effectiveness of wellness programs. This can be done through surveys, focus groups, or other assessment methods. Regularly review and analyze the collected data to gain insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the programs. Use this information to make informed adjustments and enhancements to optimize the impact of the initiatives.

Provide training programs to teachers to assist them acclimatize to the requirements of face-to-face classes after they have spent a considerable amount of time participating in distance learning. These training programs must incorporate techniques for promoting a healthy work-life balance, such as managing one's time effectively, dealing with one's stress, and communicating effectively with one's coworkers and administrators.

To help teachers better manage their workload and minimize inter-role conflict, encourage them to adopt self-efficacy and other cognitive coping mechanisms. Setting goals, engaging in positive self-talk, and making a list of priorities are all effective strategies that might help teachers feel more in control of their job and lessen the possibility of being burned out.

Design and put into action the intervention programs tailored fit to the needs of individual teachers and addressed to the multifaceted aspects of work-life balance, such as programs that promote physical and mental health, work-related assistance, and personal growth and development toward achieving a better balance between work and personal responsibilities.

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